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Acronyms and abbreviations

%-wt	mass percentage	IL	anonymisation of one of the 4 laboratories doing the ICP analyses of char
AA	Ammonium Acetate	LHV	Calorific Value
ASE	Accelerated Solvent Extraction	LiC	Left in Char
BET	Brunauer-Emmett-Teller	LoD	Limit of Detection
Analysis		LoQ	Limit of Quantification
BiV	Batch <i>in Vitro</i> open system leaching experiments	L/S	Liquid to Solid ratio
CA	Citric Acid	MA	Miscanthus Ash
CHS	Carbon / Hydrogen / Sulphur Analyzer	MB	Mass Balance
CHSNO	Carbon / Hydrogen / Sulphur / Nitrogen / Oxygen Analyzer	MMX	Miscanthus Mix
CT	Cuvette Tests	n.m.	not measured
CW	Clean Wood	NMR	Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
DW	Demolition Wood	OA	Oxalic Acid
EDTA	EthyleneDiamineTetraacetic Acid	PPNT	anonymisation of one of the 4 laboratories doing the ICP analyses of char
ETL	anonymisation of one of the 4 laboratories doing the ICP analyses of char	PR	Pressure Reactor
FC	Fixed Carbon	RF	Recovered Fraction
ICP	Inductively Coupled Plasma	RMS	Root Mean Square
ICP-OES	Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectroscopy	SGR	Switchgrass
IETU	anonymisation of one of the 4 laboratories doing the ICP analyses of char	TGA	Thermogravimetric analysis
		US	Ultrasound
		VM	Volatile Matter
		XRD	X-Ray Diffraction
		XRF	X-Ray Fluorescence

Acronyms used to identify consortium members

ECODESIGN	Ecodesign Company Engineering & Management Consultancy GmbH
RIC	Centrum Badań i Innowacji Pro-Akademia Stowarzyszenie
VTT	Teknologian Tutkimuskeskus VTT OY

1 Publishable executive summary

This report presents the results of the first part of the research work performed to explore the recovery of valuable elements from solid gasification residues (char, ashes) via leaching. This research was implemented as a part of the work in WP7 of the BeBOP project (WP7, *Enabling technologies at lab-scale for SOEC characterisation and resource recovery, T7.2, Recovery elements from solid gasification residues via leaching*).

Depending on the type and origin of the biomass, char will contain a certain fraction of valuable inorganic elements, including nutrients and (heavy) metals. Some of the elements found in relevant biomass types are included in the 5th list of Critical Raw Materials for the EU, e.g., phosphorus, magnesium, aluminium. Although their shares in the gasification residues are relatively low, from ppm up to percent levels, taking into account the long-term operation of the gasification plant these quantities accumulate and become substantial. In addition to value extraction, the recovery of elements from the gasification residues, prevents hazardous waste accumulation, thereby improving the overall sustainability and circularity of the bio-/e-methanol production.

The goal of this research work was to study the separation (recovery) of the inorganic constituents of biomass char and ash via the leaching process while applying different process conditions. The base case experiments were batch experiments performed *in vitro*. The char samples from four different biomass types (clean wood, demolition wood, Miscanthus and hay) were obtained in the laboratory, while the ash sample was obtained during the gasification of Miscanthus. The leaching agents used involved water, citric acid, oxalic acid, hydrochloric acid, sodium hydroxide, ammonium acetate, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) and water peroxide. Different leaching sequences were investigated, starting from a multi-step water leaching with intermediate char drying, through the leaching with the above-mentioned leaching agents after an initial water leaching step, and finally a 3-step process involving water, ammonium acetate and hydrochloric acid. In the base case experiments different leaching temperatures (25°C and 60°C) and leaching times (1, 5 and 60 minutes) were applied. In the first series (Miscanthus ash leaching) also the leaching time of 24 hours was used, and an experiment with ultrasound assisted leaching was done. In total 61 multi-step batch experiments were done. Furthermore, also different process devices were tested. A short series of experiments was carried out using a pressurized batch reactor in order to investigate the effect of elevated temperature, pressure and different gaseous atmospheres above the leachate, as well as to identify any gases possibly being released during leaching. Next, the Accelerated Solvent Extraction (ASE) device was used to explore the water leaching process limits, with high pressure, different temperatures and short residence times.

After the experiments the chemical composition of the leachate was analysed, which allowed the calculation of the recovery fraction (RF) of each considered element. All leachate samples were analysed using the cuvette tests for a narrow range of elements. In addition, selected leachate samples and selected samples of char exposed to leaching were analysed using ICP-OES.

In order to obtain a better understanding of the leaching process and to be able to select the process conditions in a more targeted way, a chemical equilibrium-based model of the leaching process using the FactSage software was implemented and a series of simulations was done.

The analysis of the experimental results showed that selective separation of different elements is possible. Starting with water leaching allows to recover water-soluble elements (K, P, S, Na), although the recovered fractions differ among these elements. The effect of the leaching time is less pronounced than the effect of the temperature. It was also revealed that an important gain in leaching performance is achieved by the intermediate drying of the substrate and repeating the leaching step. This allowed to achieve high recovery fractions with only short exposure times (order of 1 minute) of the substrate to the leaching agent. Heavy metals were barely recovered with water, which is good from the separation point of view. Here an inverse effect of the leaching temperature was observed on lead: its amount in the leachate dropped with the increasing leaching temperature, which can later be used as a parameter to control the separation of the elements.

Summarising the results of the first set of the FactSage simulations and their validation against the experimental results it can be concluded that the simulations based on chemical equilibrium and Gibbs' free energy minimization can provide useful insight during the development of the leaching process and the recovery of valuable elements from biomass char and ash. The obtained set of results gave multiple suggestions for the required focal points of the research to be implemented during the next stages of the project, namely to gain the information about the specific compounds present in the char or ash matrix, getting additional information about the ash chemistry and phase diagrams of the species of interest.

In general, it can be concluded that each leaching sequence will start with water leaching, likely followed by the second water of ammonium acetate step to remove all potassium, chlorine and sulphur. Then, preferably other nutrient elements (phosphorus, magnesium, calcium) should be recovered, finally followed by other (heavy) metals. At this stage it is not yet possible to draw conclusions about the procedures for other important elements present in the char and ash, namely silicon and aluminium. Their mobilisation into the leachate as its justification is yet to be investigated. The exact process equipment (open system or pressurized reactor) is still to be defined. The open system performed relatively well considering its simplicity, but high temperature (200°C) and pressurized conditions had a significant positive effect on the recovery fraction of potassium and sulphur. Likely solely the higher RFs of these two elements will not justify the engagement of such more complex equipment, but the final choice will depend on the overall recovery scheme and any possible process integrations (e.g., thermal integration) with the gasification or the entire bio/e-methanol production facility.

The results obtained in this part of the project will be used for the further investigation of the recovery of the elements via leaching, namely in WP8 of the project (WP8, *Technology validation: SOEC and gasification residues recovery*, T8.2, *Leaching conditions validation*).

2 Introduction

The main product of biomass gasification is combustible gas – producer gas, which after cleaning and upgrading can become syngas. Nonetheless, there are always also solid residues, which presence is inherent to the characteristics of the fuel (ash) and the conversion process (char). Clean woody fuels will yield the lowest amounts of ash (typically below 0.5%-wt of the input biomass), while when using biomass of herbaceous origin the amount of ash will be significantly higher, several percent-points or more. The amount of char will strictly depend on the type of the gasification process and the applied process parameters, which are also linked to the type of fuel used. For a circulating fluidized bed gasifier at a scale of 100 MW thermal input, which in this project is considered as the target scale, the amount of char (unconverted carbon and the inorganics from the biomass feed) is estimated at 4.5%-wt of the biomass input [1], which gives approximately 1.1 ton of char per hour of gasifier operation. Depending on the type and origin of the biomass, char will contain a certain fraction of valuable inorganic elements, including nutrients and (heavy) metals. Some of the elements found in relevant biomass types are included in the 5th list of Critical Raw Materials for the EU, namely phosphorus, magnesium, bauxite (aluminium), feldspars (aluminium tectosiliactes, often bound to potassium, sodium or calcium), but also silicon metal or coking coal [2]. Although their shares in the char vary from ppm up to percent levels, taking into account the hourly mass stream of the char and long-term operation of the gasification plant these quantities accumulate and become relevant. It is one of the developments that one or two decades ago would be considered absurd, but is now gaining momentum due to its possible contribution to the shift from the linear to the circular economy, and the awareness of the need to reduce the dependency on the remote natural resources.

The “BeBOP solution” aims to close the loop and maximize the use of the resources, including the recovery of key elements from solid gasification residues mentioned above. The use of the biochar, for example as a fertilizer, and the recovery of heavy metals are included in the expected outcomes of the project. The project envisages the investigation of different recovery paths, one based on leaching and the other based on innovative recovery pathways other than leaching. The goal of the research work implemented in this part of the BeBOP project is to study the feasibility of the recovery processes of (trace) elements, and to obtain new knowledge about which processes, sequences and conditions need to be applied for a specific residue to achieve the desired recovery, so at the end of the project a concept for the recovery of selected valuable elements and/or compounds, validated on the laboratory scale can be proposed.

This report presents the results of the first part of the research work performed to explore the recovery of valuable elements from solid gasification residues (char, ashes) via leaching. This research was implemented as a part of the work in WP7 of the BeBOP project (WP7, *Enabling technologies at lab-scale for SOEC characterisation and resource recovery, T7.2, Recovery elements from solid gasification residues via leaching*), and included experimental laboratory work as well as modelling and simulations.

3 Biomass and char characterization

3.1 The structure of raw biomass – an overview

The composition and structure of biomass fundamentally determines its behaviour during pyrolysis and gasification, influencing both the decomposition of organic components and the transformation of inorganic matter. These characteristics affect not only the yield and composition of the resulting solid products (chars and ashes), but also the chemical forms of elements that directly influence their chemical and physical properties, among other also the leaching behaviour. Understanding these relationships is essential for predicting element migration from the raw biomass to the char and ash, and further its susceptibility for leaching as well as the optimization of the recovery strategies. The latter two topics are the focal point of the investigation of the leaching methods presented and discussed in the further sections of this report.

The five types of biomass selected for the analysis in this study – woody biomass (CW, DW), herbaceous biomass (MMX, SG) and mixed grassy biomass (HAY) - significantly differ in terms of anatomical structure, lignocellulosic composition, and the way inorganic elements are incorporated into plant tissues.

MMX represents the biomass of a perennial grass with a heterogeneous structure. Miscanthus is a well-known energy crop. The material is composed of vascular bundles embedded in parenchyma tissue, while the epidermis contains characteristic silica bodies. As demonstrated in numerous studies on Miscanthus, the leaves and stems are different in terms of the proportions of cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin, as well as the distribution of minerals. This internal variability makes inorganic compounds get built into the tissues differently, which influences how thermal decomposition happens and how carbon-rich structures form during pyrolysis [1].

CW is the most homogeneous raw material in terms of structure in the analysed group. Its lignocellulosic skeleton consists of tracheids, fibres, vessels, and ray parenchyma arranged in an organized way. The inorganic fraction in wood is low and usually associated with cell wall components. Due to this homogeneity, CW exhibits predictable thermal properties, producing char with a relatively organized carbon matrix and limited mineral content [2].

Hay consists of thin stems, leaves, and husks characterized by high hemicellulose content and thin-walled pulp. Mineral elements (K, Ca, Mg, P, S) are usually located near the surface or in small vessels. Anatomical variability between tissue types leads to differences in decomposition during heating. This results in less ordered areas of carbon and dispersion of minerals in the solid residue [3].

DW retains the primary lignocellulosic features of natural wood; however, it exhibits the highest structural heterogeneity among the analysed feedstocks. This variability results from age-related degradation, prior mechanical or environmental exposure, and the presence of surface treatments such as coatings, preservatives or adhesives. These modifications may alter local cell wall morphology, affect porosity, and introduce irregularities in the spatial distribution of inorganic matter.

In addition, DW can contain both physical and chemical impurities, including residual metals, pigments, fillers, salts or construction-related additives. Their occurrence depends strongly on the origin and quality grade of the material. As a consequence, DW often includes locally elevated concentrations of trace elements or non-native compounds. These combined making DW the most diverse feedstock in terms of both microstructure and mineral content [4]. Nonetheless, the content of inorganic matter (ash) and its elemental composition is typically closer to other woody biomass than to the representatives of herbaceous biomass.

SG is a perennial grass, just as Miscanthus often cultivated as an energy crop. It is characterised by a fibrous anatomical structure with well-defined lignified vascular bundles surrounded by parenchyma. The epidermis contains abundant silica phytoliths, which are typical for warm-season grasses. Compositional differences between plant organs are pronounced: stems have higher cellulose and lignin content, whereas leaves contain more hemicellulose and exhibit increased concentrations of mineral nutrients such as K, Ca and Mg. As reported in recent studies, switchgrass also shows

developmental variability in cell wall composition and lignification patterns, which leads to spatial heterogeneity in both organic constituents and inorganic species. The mineral fraction typically includes silica, potassium salts and calcium- or magnesium-based compounds, with levels depending on plant age and growth conditions [5].

In summary, the analysed biomass raw materials show clear structural and compositional differences, both in terms of anatomical structure and the distribution of lignocellulosic and mineral components. These differences determine how inorganic elements are incorporated into plant tissues and have a strong influence on the course of thermal decomposition. Therefore, the properties of the resulting char—such as porosity, degree of carbon ordering, and location of mineral residues—can be directly correlated with the properties of the raw materials. Understanding these relationships provides an important context for interpreting the leaching results presented in the following chapters of this report.

3.2 Char and ash characteristics relevant to the separation of individual elements via leaching

An understanding of the structure and composition of char and ash is necessary to predict how individual elements can be separated by leaching, as well as to assess the recovery potential (the absolute amount of an element per unit mass of the substrate) and the recovered fraction (i.e. the amount of an element removed / recovered from the char or the ash). Although pyrolysis and combustion transform mostly the organic fraction of biomass, these processes also change the way in which inorganic components are concentrated, distributed, and chemically bound in the solid residue. For this reason, the following analyses: TGA, CHNSO, BET, XRD, and ICP-OES are used for interpretation not only in terms of thermal behaviour, but primarily in direct relation to the leaching potential of elements in later processing stages. The information provided in this section is a summary of the analyses relevant to the study of the leaching process. The full description can be found in the deliverable D7.3, *Characterisation of biomass samples* [6].

TGA and calorimetric data provide a quick indication of how much mineral matter becomes concentrated in the char after pyrolysis. Since at 550°C most of the volatile organic components are removed, the inorganic fraction becomes proportionally enriched. Nonetheless, char originating from biomass with initially low ash content (e.g., CW, DW) will still contain only relatively small amounts of minerals, whereas ash-rich feedstocks (MMX, HAY) show substantial increases of the ash percentage.

This behaviour is important for the leaching process:

- low-ash chars contain lower absolute amounts of the extractable components and will likely require further processing (e.g. additional oxidation to remove the bulk carbon load) in order to expose these minerals to the leaching process,
- high-ash chars are naturally richer in inorganic species, which should in theory improve their availability for the leaching, in comparison to the low-ash char.

The values in Table 1 illustrate these differences in volatile matter (VM), fixed carbon (FC) and lower heating value (LHV), highlighting how much of the solid fraction remains carbon-dominated versus mineral-rich after pyrolysis.

Table 1. The results of thermogravimetric analysis and calorimetry. Abbreviations: VM – volatile matter, FC – fixed carbon, LHV – lower heating value. All values reported on “as received” basis. (n.m. – not measured)

Feedstock	Moisture [%-wt]	Ash [%-wt]	VM [%-wt]	FC [%-wt]	LHV [MJ/kg]
MA Ash	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.
MMX Char	0.713±0.119	9.20±0.11	10.5±1.1	79.6±1.0	30.5±0.1
CW Char	0.89±0.03	1.09±0.12	12.8±0.9	85.3±0.9	33.3±0.3

Feedstock	Moisture [%-wt]	Ash [%-wt]	VM [%-wt]	FC [%-wt]	LHV [MJ/kg]
HAY Char	3.39±0.04	26.2±0.2	17.2±1.1	53.3±1.2	22.1±0.2
DW Char	2.48±0.11	2.31±0.21	14.9±1.1	80.3±1.0	32.6±0.2

The CHNSO results are presented in Table 2. The strong increase in carbon content in MMX, CW, and DW char (above 90%) shows that the material matrix becomes strongly dominated by this element. In practice, this means that most of the minerals present in the biomass can become “trapped” in the carbon structure, therefore making them difficult for the leaching solution to access.

Table 2. The results of elemental analyses CHNSO. All values on “as received” basis. Feedstocks arranged by the increasing carbon (C) content.

Feedstock	C [%-wt]	H [%-wt]	N [%-wt]	S [%-wt]	O [%-wt]
MA Ash	61.4±0.5	1.10±0.16	n.m.	0.113±0.005	8.11
HAY Char	67.1±0.6	1.70±0.02	n.m.	0.225±0.007	n.m.
MMX Char	90.9±0.4	1.99±0.01	<LOD	0.108±0.005	10.38
DW Char	96.3±0.3	2.44±0.07	n.m.	0.055±0.007	n.m.
CW Char	98.7±0.4	2.28±0.04	<LOD	0.0034±0.001	10.31

On the other hand, materials with lower carbon content and higher amounts of other non-carbon elements, such as HAY char or MA ash, typically have a more open and accessible form of inorganic components. This is expected to make the leaching process more effective.

Showing the differences is important for the planning of further leaching stages: high-carbon char may need an extra step, like oxidation or pre-treatment to achieve higher enrichment of the target elements in the bulk, while low-carbon char and ash are expected to be achieve good leaching efficiencies even when leached directly.

To evaluate the textural properties of the studied materials, the Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) surface area and average pore size were determined. The results are summarized in Table 3. This analysis provides insight into the degree of pore structure development in the ash and char samples obtained from different biomass feedstocks.

Table 3. BET surface area and pore size of the investigated feedstocks; carbon content (C) added for reference. Values sorted by the increasing C.

Feedstock	BET Surface Area [m ² /g]	Pore Size [Å]	C [%-wt]
MA Ash	256.2	0.979	61.4±0.5
HAY Char	347.3	16.24	67.1±0.6
MMX Char	317.7	17.29	90.9±0.4
DW Char	10.4	0.975	96.3±0.3
CW Char	418.1	17.25	98.7±0.4

The highest BET surface area was obtained for CW Char (418.1 m²/g), indicating a highly developed porous structure. Slightly lower values were observed for MMX Char (317.7 m²/g), while MA Ash exhibited a smaller, yet still relatively high surface area (256.2 m²/g) for an ash-derived material. Both types of char displayed similar pore sizes (~17 Å, 1 Å = 0.1 nm), confirming the predominance of mesopores typically formed during biomass pyrolysis.

HAY char also showed a well-developed mesoporous structure, with a BET surface area of 347.3 m²/g and an average pore size of approximately 16 Å, placing it between MMX and CW Char in terms of porosity. In contrast, DW Char exhibited a very low surface area (10.4 m²/g) and a pore diameter below 1 Å, indicating a highly compacted or poorly developed pore network. Such textural collapse is consistent with heterogeneous feedstocks that may contain coatings or resins which limit pore formation during pyrolysis.

The very small pore diameter of MMX Ash (0.979 Å) may result from fine micropores or the presence of silica- and oxide-based structures, which are fused together due to the exposure to higher temperatures (700 – 800°C), as well as the absence of the bulk carbonaceous structure. Overall, the results confirm that the pyrolysis process leads to the formation of materials with a highly developed surface area and favourable sorption properties.

Despite the higher BET surface area of char, element leaching is generally more efficient from ash. This is consistent with literature data showing that biochars, rich in carbon and characterised by high sorption capacity, tend to retain nutrients and metals and thus limit their mobility, whereas biomass ashes consist mainly of discrete mineral phases (oxides, phosphates, salts) that can be relatively easily dissolved and processed for element recovery [7].

These observations highlight the strong relationship between the textural and structural characteristics of the materials and their expected leaching performance. To further verify these assumptions and identify the crystalline or amorphous nature of the solids, X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was performed.

In addition to the results presented in Deliverable 7.3, Chapter 5.2.2.2, which discussed the XRD spectra of MMX and CW biomass and MMX and CW char, an additional comparative analysis of the spectra of MMX Char (**Figure 1**) and MMX Ash (**Figure 2**) was carried out, taking into account their significance for the subsequent stages of leaching and thermodynamic equilibrium simulations.

Figure 1. XRD spectrum of MMX Char. [Source: RIC]

Figure 2. XRD spectrum of MA Ash. [Source: RIC]

According to previous observations, MMX Char exhibited broad, blurred diffraction bands with a maximum in the range of $\sim 20\text{--}25^\circ 2\Theta$ and a weaker arm at $\sim 33\text{--}36^\circ 2\Theta$, typical of amorphous carbon. The absence of obvious crystalline reflections confirms the ordered structure and dominance of carbon forms in which mineral components are dispersed and partially integrated into the carbon matrix. This structure complicates the contact of components with leaching solutions, reducing the mobility of elements, which is confirmed in the literature on biochar and biomass pyrolysis products [8].

In the case of the MMX Ash sample, numerous well-defined crystal reflections corresponding to KCl (sylvite), Al_2O_3 , phosphates of Mn, Ca, Fe, Mg, and Li were observed. The presence of these phases indicates the clearly crystalline, inorganic nature of the material and the significant removal of the carbon matrix during the gasification process. The presence of such structures promotes greater solubility of elements in aqueous and acidic solutions, which directly contributes to higher leaching efficiency [9].

In the context of planned thermodynamic simulations (FactSage), the results obtained suggest that char should be treated as a mixture of amorphous carbon and disordered oxides, while ash can be modelled based on specific crystalline phases with known solubility constants. From the point of view of designing a process for recovering elements, it is reasonable to consider the possibility to move directly to the combustion stage or to use preliminary oxidation of char, which facilitates the “release” of elements and increases their leachability [10].

In Deliverable 7.3 it was shown that ICP-OES analyses performed in three external laboratories (ETL, IL, PPNT) showed relatively consistent qualitative trends, but large quantitative discrepancies for many elements. In particular, absolute concentrations of major elements such as K, Ca, Mg and P differed by up to an order of magnitude between laboratories, even though the same homogenised samples were used. These differences can be attributed mainly to variations in digestion procedures and their completeness (aqua regia vs. HNO_3), matrix effects related to the heterogeneous, high carbon content of the chars, and instrumental factors (spectrometer type, line selection, background correction). As a result, the repeatability and reproducibility of the ICP-OES data across laboratories are limited, especially for elements associated with silicate. To verify this, samples were sent to a fourth, independent laboratory for additional verification (IETU). The results are closest to the results by ETL and although this strengthens the choice of the ETL dataset as the reference (raw char) composition, still the uncertainty is high and an additional investigation is necessary in this context, which is planned.

Complete ICP-OES data sets from all laboratories are presented in Appendix I.

3.3 Characteristics of individual elements and their predominant compounds predominant in the biomass ash and char

In Section 3.2 the composition of different kinds of biomass and their chars and ashes were described, zooming in from the plant anatomy, through proximate analysis to the elemental composition, including the major components (C, H, N, S, O) and the inorganic (ash) constituents. For further interpretation of the leaching experiments and the influence of different leaching parameters it is also important to know the characteristics of the individual elements, including their occurrence in nature and the most common reactions and reaction products. A brief description of the main inorganic constituents of the biomass char and ash, namely silicon (Si), aluminium (Al), potassium (K), chlorine (Cl) and phosphorus (P) is given below.

3.3.1 Silicon (Si)¹

Silicon is the second most abundant element on Earth, after oxygen. Pure silicon is very reactive, therefore in nature it occurs either as SiO₂ (silica) or forms compounds with other elements, mainly with Al, Mg, Ca, Na, K or Fe, called silicates. Silicon-containing compounds are very stable, since the energy binding the nuclei (protons and electrons) is ca. 8.4 MeV; for comparison, iron (Fe) has the maximum binding energy (8.7 MeV), but its nucleus is twice as massive.

Silicon and its compounds occur in the nature both as crystalline and as amorphous atomic structures. Examples of crystalline minerals are quartz, cristobalite, tridymite, while agate, opal, chalcedony are amorphous. Crystalline Si was for the first time prepared using electrolysis in 1854.

Elemental silicon is produced via the reduction of SiO₂ with coke, or (on a small scale) via the reduction with Al. Almost pure Si is obtained by the reduction of SiCl₃ (trichlorsilane).

Silicon as an element exhibits many similarities with carbon (C). Si is relatively chemically inactive at ambient temperatures, but when heated it reacts vigorously with halogens (F, Cl, Br, I) and certain metals. Due to strong bonds it is unaffected by acids, except HF (hydrofluoric acid). At very high temperatures (2000 – 2600°C) Si reacts with C to form SiC (silicon carbide). With hydrogen Si forms hydrides (silanes), having the general formula Si_nH_{2n + 2}. The silanes are structural analogues of the saturated hydrocarbons (alkanes) but are much less stable. With hydrocarbon groups Si forms organic Si compounds.

Silicon and its compounds are widely used in various industries:

- pure Si: semiconductors etc.;
- less pure: metallurgy as reducing agent, alloying element in steel, aluminium, brass, bronze;
- bricks, concrete, refractory materials;
- quarts, glassware;
- silicates – most of them insoluble in water -> ceramic materials;
- Na-silicates (“glass water”) -> soaps, wood treatment, cement, dye;
- silicones (synthetic organosilicon oxides, consisting of Si, O, C, H) – lubricants, hydraulic fluids, etc. These compounds are chemically inert and stable at high temperatures.

3.3.2 Aluminium (Al)²

In nature the element occurs mainly in aluminosilicates, while bauxite is the main Al ore, which is used to produce Al in metallic form. Amorphous Al oxides are present in gemstones (ruby, sapphire, topaz, etc.), while crystalline forms are the constituents of, e.g., emery and corundum. Alunite and cryolite have some commercial importance. Laterite is an Fe-rich Al-containing mineral.

Crude Al was first isolated by reducing AlCl₃ with K amalgam. Another pathway (the Deville process) is the reduction of molten AlCl₃ with Na. Currently the commonly used production process is the electrolysis of purified Al₂O₃ dissolved in molten cryolite (Na₃AlF₆). Pure 99.996% Al is soft and weak, but with small amounts of Si and Fe (then 99.6% pure, commercial grade) it gains the desired hardness and strength. Al is chemically attacked by acids and rapidly dissolves in HCl. Concentrated HNO₃, however,

¹ This paragraph is a summary of the article in Encyclopedia Britannica [30]

² This paragraph is a summary of the article in Encyclopedia Britannica [31]

passifies the metal. The metal is also vigorously attacked by alkalis (NaOH, KOH) to produce gaseous H₂ and Al⁻ ions. Al has very high O affinity and will react with CO or CO₂ to form Al₂O₃ and AlC. Al is inert to S, even up to high temperatures.

Although Al³⁺ ion is known to occur (e.g. AlCl₃, AlF₃), the energy to form the ion is very high, and therefore covalent compounds are preferred from an energy point of view. Al³⁺ can be stabilized by hydration as Al(H₂O)₆³⁺.

Anodic Al-oxide (AAO) produced via electrochemical oxidation of Al is a nanostructured Al-based material with a unique pore structure suitable e.g. for the synthesis of nanotubes and nanorods. Al₂(SO₄)₃ is an important commercial chemical used in paper manufacturing as a binder for dyes. Al₂(SO₄)₃ + M^(l+)₂SO₄ react to M₂Al(SO₄)₂*12 H₂O; these double salts are called alums, with M being a singly charged cation as K⁺, Na⁺, Rb⁺, Ce⁺, NH₄⁺ or Tl⁺. Al can be replaced by other 3+ cations, Ga, In, Ti, V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co. The most important of such salts is AlKSO₄ (potassium alum), which has many applications in the production of medicines, textiles and paints.

Gaseous chlorine with liquid Al produces AlCl₃, which is widely used as a catalyst in Friedel-Craft reactions. Hydrated AlCl₃*H₂O is used in deodorants, it's one of the Al salts used in cosmetics industry. Al(OH)₃ is used to waterproof fabrics and produce other Al-compounds including aluminates (salts containing AlO- group).

With H₂, AlH₃ (Al-hydride) is formed, a polymeric solid, from which tetrahydroaluminates are derived, these are important reducing agents. LiAlH₄, formed from AlCl₃ and LiH is widely used in organic chemistry.

3.3.3 Potassium (K)³

Potassium belongs to the alkali metals group in the periodic table of elements. It is indispensable for both plant and animal life. K is naturally present in igneous rocks (solidified molten earth material), shale and sediment minerals, like muscovite and orthoclase feldspar, the latter being insoluble in water. Commercial K-compounds are obtained via electrolysis from soluble K-compounds such as carnallite (KMgCl₃*6H₂O), sylvite (KCl), polyhalite K₂Ca₂Mg(SO₄)₄*2H₂O or Langbeinite K₂Mg₂(SO₄)₃.

There is little industrial demand for solid, metallic K, as is readily oxidised to KO₂. KO₂, however, is used in respiratory equipment as it releases oxygen when removing CO₂ and water vapour and forming KHCO₃.

Main compounds involving K are KCl, KOH, KI, KNO₃, K₂SO₄ and K₂CrO₄. K (contrary to Na) reacts with graphite to form a series of interlamellar compounds, the richest having the formula KC₈ (and then KC₁₆, KC₂₄ etc).

At low temperatures (around 60°C) K reacts with CO to form the explosive K₆C₆O₆. At high temperatures K reduces CO₂ to CO, solid C, while forming KO₂.

3.3.4 Chlorine (Cl)⁴

Chlorine is a toxic, corrosive, greenish gas with a boiling point of -34°C. In the past HCl was obtained by heating moist NaCl in a charcoal furnace and condensing the fumes (NaCl was converted to Na₂CO₃ and the formed Cl reacted with water vapor to form HCl. Later this was done by heating NaCl with H₂SO₄. The reaction of HCl with MnO gave Cl (g).

Gaseous chlorine occurs in nature only in volcanic gases, apart from that the element is found in chemical compounds only. Most common naturally occurring compound is rock salt (NaCl), but also minerals sylvite (KCl), bischofite (MgCl₂*6H₂O), kainite (KCl*MgSO₄*3H₂O). KCl has a greater water solubility than NaCl and is also important as a fertilizer.

Cl has a very high electronegativity and electron affinity. The affinity for H₂ is very high, so that the reaction proceeds explosively in light. This high affinity allows Cl to react with many species containing H. In hydrocarbons H is substituted by Cl, but in unsaturated HCs the Cl atoms are added to double or

³ This paragraph is a summary of the article in Encyclopedia Britannica [32]

⁴ This paragraph is a summary of the article in Encyclopedia Britannica [33]

triple bonds. Cl reacts with almost all elements, except the lighter noble gases, to form chlorides. Metals yield ionic crystals, whereas nonmetals and semimetals are mainly molecular.

Usually, high oxidation number chlorides are formed (e.g. FeCl_3 , SnCl_4 , SbCl_5). It is noteworthy that higher oxidation numbers exist for F than for Cl (e.g. SF_6 , but no SCl_6 , and even SCl_4 is unstable). Except the “-1” oxidation state, Cl exhibits also positive oxidation states.

Cl displaces other, heavier, less electronegative halogens from their compounds. It also converts some oxides to chlorides, e.g. $2 \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 + 6 \text{Cl} \rightarrow 4 \text{FeCl}_3 + 3 \text{O}_2$.

Cl is produced by electrolysis of an aqueous solution of NaCl, yielding gaseous H_2 , Cl_2 and leaving NaOH in the solution phase. When using a Hg cathode, then free Na is formed at the cathode and it readily dissolves in the Hg forming an amalgam. This amalgam can subsequently react with H_2O to form $\text{NaOH}(\text{aq}) + \text{H}_2$ – in this configuration no membranes between the cathode and the anode are necessary, but of course the drawback of this process is that it involves highly toxic Hg.

Most insoluble chlorides can be melted with Na_2CO_3 (soda) and the resulting melt is usually soluble in water. Organic compounds containing Cl are heated with alkali peroxide and the product is dissolved in H_2O .

Industrially Cl is relevant to the production of chlorinated HCs (e.g. CCl_4), PVC, dyes and synthetic rubber. SCl is used for vulcanization of rubber. CO and Cl combine to COCl_2 (phosgene). SO_2 is used to produce sulfuryl dioxide (SO_2Cl_2). Bleaching powder ($\text{Ca}[\text{OCl}]_2 \cdot \text{CaCl}_2 \cdot \text{Ca}[\text{OH}]_2 \cdot 2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$).

Cl is used for the extraction of Ti as TiCl_4 and for the removal of Sn. AlCl_3 is made by reacting Cl with Al or with Al_2O_3 and C. Also SiCl_4 and CH_3Cl are important in the synthesis of silicon materials.

3.3.5 Phosphorus (P)⁵

Phosphorus at room conditions is a colourless, semi-transparent soft solid, that glows in the dark. Its melting temperature 44.1°C . Due to high reactivity it does not occur on Earth in a free state, but as a phosphate (PO_4^{3-}) ion. P can be produced from phosphoric acid upon distillation and heating with charcoal. About 550 minerals have been found to contain P, but the principal source of P is apatite, where Ca and P coexist, together with F, Cl, OH: general formula is $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{F}/\text{Cl}/\text{OH})_2$.

The key commercial source of P is phosphorite (phosphate rock), a carbonate-bearing apatite. 80% of this mineral available on Earth are found in Morocco and Western Sahara. Principal production method relies on the treatment of the crushed rock with either H_2SO_4 or H_3PO_4 to form Ca,H-phosphates, which are water-soluble and therefore form valuable additions to fertilizers. Most of the output is burned to phosphoric anhydride (P_4O_{10}) and subsequently treated with water to form H_3PO_4 . Except the fertilizer, it is also a threat for the aquatic systems, as it can cause increased growth of algae. Besides, it is a non-renewable resource, therefore the recycling of phosphorus-containing materials or the extraction of P from waste streams is of key importance for the long-term stability of P supply.

P can have oxidation states +3 (also +5 is possible) and -3. Pure element exists in 10 allotropic forms, all solid. The three main ones are red, white and black. P_2 (triple bonds) exists only at $T < 1200^\circ\text{C}$, below it condenses to form tetrahedral P_4 . White P (alpha) has a cubic crystal structure at room temperature. The beta form, which is stable below -78°C has a hexagonal crystal structure. Above 200°C the structure changes spontaneously to a polymeric form called red P. Red P is amorphous, but can become crystalline. At a high pressure and temperature, or with a catalyst closer to ambient conditions, P is converted to a flaky black crystalline form – this could be the most stable form of P. In both red and black P each atom forms 3 single bonds. White P is the most reactive (and toxic). It ignites in air at only 35°C . White P dissolves in CS_2 , where it maintains the P_4 structure. Red P is insoluble and relatively inert, nonetheless it can ignite and react with H_2O to form phosphine (PH_3). Black P is more inert and can conduct electricity.

PH_3 is used as starting material in the synthesis of various organic P compounds, as a doping agent for solid-state electronics and as a fumigant. Although very toxic, it must not be confused with phosgene (COCl_2), the WW I chemical weapon.

P_4O_{10} is used as a dehydrating agent, or to make H_3PO_4 . $\text{Ca}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_2$ is the most widely used P fertilizer. With halogen elements it forms various halides (PX_3 with X being F, Cl, Br and I; also PX_5 with F, Cl, Br).

⁵ This paragraph is a summary of the article in Encyclopedia Britannica [34]

The solids PCl_5 and PBr_5 contain PX^{4+} and PX^{6-} ions rather than PX_5 molecules. P reacts with S to form sulphides used in organic chemicals and matches. P reacts with many metals to form phosphides. P can bond with O to form ester groups, which can bond with C atoms giving a large number of organic P chemicals.

3.3.6 Calcium (Ca)⁶

Most common form of calcium in nature is the calcite or calcium carbonate, CaCO_3 , and it is also the most important Ca compound. Calcite dissolves in water that contains CO_2 , to form $\text{Ca}(\text{HCO}_3)_2$. Pure metal was first isolated by the electrolysis of a mixture of lime (CaO) and HgO.

Except natural minerals (e.g. apatite), Ca is present as hydroxyl phosphate in teeth and bones. CaF in fluorite. In CaSO_4 in anhydrite (another form of CaSO_4 is gypsum). Also found in many feldspars (Al-Si minerals containing Ca, Na or K) and zeolites (hydrated Al-Si minerals containing alkali and earth-alkali metals).

Pure element was formerly produced by electrolysis of anhydrous CaCl_2 , now it is done via the heating of lime with Al. Ca reacts slowly with O_2 , water vapour and N_2 and forms a yellow coating of the oxide, hydroxide and nitride, respectively. It reacts rapidly with liquid water to produce H_2 and CaOH (slacked lime). Upon heating it reacts with H_2 , halogens, B, S, C and P. It compares favourably with Na as a reducing agent, but is more expensive and less reactive than the latter. Nonetheless it is used to prepare Cr, Th, U, Zr and other metals from their oxides (as an reducing agent). Ca is used as an alloying agent for Al, Cu, Pb, Mg and other base metals.

Despite abundant natural occurrence, synthetic ("precipitated") CaCO_3 is employed when high purity is required. At room temperature CaO (quicklime) will spontaneously absorb CO_2 to form CaCO_3 . It will also absorb water to form CaOH (slacked lime) and release heat. CaO is also used to produce CaC_2 (calcium carbide). CaC_2 in water will form C_2H_2 and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$. CaC_2 is also used to make CaCN_2 which is a fertilizer and starting material for certain plastic resins. CaCl_2 is used as a drying agent and for the de-icing on the roads. $\text{Ca}(\text{ClO}_2)$ is widely used as bleaching powder. CaH_2 (calcium hydride) can remove traces of water from many organic solvents. CaSO_4 exists in different forms: $\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (dihydrate), or a white or colourless powder called gypsum. Upon heating to 120°C it becomes $\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Ca phosphates are the principal minerals for P-fertilizers, like $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$, $\text{Ca}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_2$. $\text{Ca}(\text{HSO}_3)_2$ is made by reacting the SO_2 and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$. This compound is used in paper industry, as under pressure it dissolves the lignin in wood, to leave cellulose fibres.

CaF_2 is important for the production of HF, which is made from CaF_2 by the action of H_2SO_4 . CaF_2 is used in lab instruments as a window material for both infrared and UV radiation.

⁶ This paragraph is a summary of the article in Encyclopedia Britannica [35]

4 Analysis of the parameters relevant to leaching

4.1 Introduction

Leaching tests are typically used to determine the mobility of inorganic and organic components from solid matrices such as ashes, chars, slags, soils or industrial wastes. In most standardized procedures, the leaching result depends on the following key parameters: leaching medium, liquid-to-solid ratio (L/S), temperature and contact time, as well as pH. The interaction of these variables determines the dominant release mechanisms (dissolution/precipitation, surface complexation, diffusion, ion exchange) and thus controls the amounts of individual elements or groups of elements that are leached [11]. The influence of these key parameters is described in the sections below.

4.2 Leaching medium

The leaching medium defines the chemical driving force for dissolution and complexation. In regulatory leaching tests, simple aqueous solutions are typically used to represent realistic or worst-case environmental scenarios. Deionized water is most commonly used as an eluent to simulate contact with groundwater or rainwater in the natural environment [12].

In addition to standard tests (demineralized H₂O), a wide range of leaching reagents are used in metal recovery studies, including:

- Mineral acids (e.g., HCl, H₂SO₄, HNO₃), which promote the dissolution of solid phases containing metals and are highly effective in leaching many heavy metals;
- Organic acids (e.g. citric, oxalic, acetic), often used to represent the effect of natural organic matter or as more gentle extractants with a strong ability to complex some cations;
- Complexing (or chelating) agents (e.g., EDTA), which increase the amount of metals moving from the solid phase to the solution;
- Alkaline solutions (e.g., NaOH), which can intensify the leaching of amphoteric elements (e.g., Al, Si) or promote the decomposition of a part of the solid material.

Many studies have shown that the composition of the leachate, and in particular its pH, has a key influence on the release of (heavy) metals. Reducing the pH usually increases the solubility and leaching of Cd, Pb, Zn, Cr, and other metals from ashes or chars. At higher pH, the mobility of many metals decreases because they form insoluble precipitates or become attached to the surface of the solid phase [13].

In this context, the leaching media used in this task include a range from aqueous solutions with a pH close to neutral, through more acidic solutions, to alkaline or complexing solutions, where appropriate. This selection of conditions enables both the representation of an environmentally relevant pH range and the assessment of the maximum mobility potential and recovery possibilities of selected metals.

4.3 Liquid to solid ratio (leaching ratio)

The liquid-to-solid ratio (L/S), usually defined as the volume or mass of the solvent / leaching agent per unit mass of dry sample and expressed in mL/g or g/g of dry mass, is one of the key parameters in leaching tests, as it influences both the degree of dilution of analytes in the solution and the efficiency of contact between the solid phase and the leachate. Increasing L/S generally leads to a decrease in metal concentrations in the eluate (leachate) (mg/L) due to dilution, but at the same time allows for the leaching of a greater amount of the element per unit of dry mass (mg/g) until a state of near equilibrium is reached [14]. Many studies on fly ash and mineral wastes have shown that, together with pH, contact time and solution composition, the L/S ratio is one of the main factors controlling the

migration of elements [15]. Studies in which fly ash has been leached at a range of L/S values (e.g. 1, 2, 5, 10, 20 and 50 mL/g) show that the largest increase in the amount of metals released occurs when moving from very low to moderate L/S values, whereas above about 10–20 mL/g further increases in the solution volume provide only a limited additional effect [16].

For fly ash, tests conducted at L/S = 10 (mL/g) are usually found in the literature. This value is often accepted as a compromise between standard leaching of the mobile fraction and the practical volume of leachate for further analysis. The importance of the L/S ratio is also confirmed by studies on other types of ash and waste. Research on biomass ash indicates that L/S – alongside pH and material properties – is one of the main factors in the long-term release of metals [17].

Important information regarding L/S also comes from work on carbonates from the pyrolysis of car tires, where L/S in the range of 10–20 mL/g was used for Zn leaching with NaOH and NaOH/H₂O₂ solutions. It was shown that increasing L/S from 10 to 20 mL/g can improve the Zn recovery rate, but at the same time leads to technological problems (mixing, high solution volume) and a loss of proportional increase in efficiency, which confirms the practical optimum of the L/S for this type of process [18]. Experimental work has shown that for the biochar suspensions in water the ratios of 5:1 or 10:1 are enough to capture the preliminary, easily mobile fraction of components and represent well the conditions of contact between the material and the water solution.

Based on the above literature results, the selection of the L/S range between 5, 10, and 20 mL/g allows for three complementary scenarios:

- L/S = 10 mL/g – a reference value widely used in ash and mineral waste leaching studies, at which representative leaching of the mobile fraction of elements is achieved with a reasonable volume of leachate;
- L/S = 5 mL/g – a scenario with limited solution inflow, similar to the conditions of material contact with water in environmental applications for biochars and carbonates, conducive to the determination of the easily soluble fraction;
- L/S = 20 mL/g – an “aggressive” scenario, corresponding to intensive contact with the solution, which is not an economical scenario from an industrial point of view.

The liquid/solid ratio defined in this way allows, on the one hand, to assess the mobility of elements in conditions similar to typical environmental contacts and, on the other hand, to determine the maximum leaching and recovery potential of selected metals from the tested material.

4.4 Temperature and contact time

Temperature and contact time together control the kinetics of leaching. In many cases, they also influence the equilibrium between the solid and liquid phases. In studies of fly ash, slag, and other mineral wastes, they are repeatedly identified, alongside pH and liquid-to-solid ratio, as the main factors that influence the rate and range of element removal [14]. Many studies on ash leaching show that higher temperatures increase the dissolution rate and metal recovery. It has been confirmed that after an initial phase of rapid release, subsequent leaching continues at a much slower rate, even for weeks or months.

The actual temperature range selected for the investigation of the influence on the leaching performance is constrained on both the low and the high side. Firstly, the temperature needs to fall within the liquid phase range, that is above the melting point and below the boiling point. A practical minimum would be the ambient temperature. Moving up towards the boiling point the evaporation rate would increase, changing the actual L/S ratio during the experiment, especially at higher contact times. Still, higher temperatures can be achieved, but this requires a closed and also a pressurized system. This would make the leaching reactor system more complicated, but would be justifiable if the corresponding process conditions would significantly increase the release of the elements into the leachate. Furthermore, when using more aggressive leaching agents, e.g., HCl or H₂O₂, the choice of the reactor materials will need to include adequate corrosion resistance, as the chemical activity of these chemicals will increase with the temperature. Therefore, next to the technical and process limitations, the maximum temperature will result from a cost/benefit analysis, taking also into account

the necessary heat input. Nonetheless, during the initial screening at the laboratory scale a relatively wide range of temperatures was chosen in order to evaluate both the conditions applicable in an “open” system, that is with a minimum evaporation of the leaching agent, as well as the more aggressive conditions, with temperatures up to 200°C using pressure reactors.

At low (i.e. close to ambient) temperatures the progress of leaching is mainly controlled by the contact time and the liquid-to-solid ratio [19]

Based on this, the contact times used in the present task – 1, 5 and 60 minutes and 24 hours – were selected to cover both the very fast initial stage of leaching and later stages that are closer to equilibrium, in a way that is relevant for environmental and industrial situations:

- **1 min** represents the immediate response of the material after first contact with the leaching solution. On this time scale, the most mobile, surface-bound or easily soluble species are washed out, similar to the initial contact with infiltrating water or the very beginning of an industrial leaching step, and consistent with short demineralised-water extractions (≈ 1 min) used in the literature to characterise the readily soluble fraction [20]
- **5 min** is a short but technically realistic contact time. At this point, a large proportion of easily soluble salts and some weakly bound metals may already be released, especially in the case of potassium, chlorides, and light metals [21] – depending on the leaching agent;
- **60 min** is an indirect contact time, often used in hydrometallurgical practice and kinetic studies. It allows for both rapid initial release and observation of the onset of slower diffusion-controlled processes, while corresponding to residence times that can be applied in industrial reactors;
- **24 hours** is viewed as a reference point, approaching the equilibrium. This time is consistent with many batch leaching protocols for ash and allows comparison of results with data from other studies conducted at similar contact times and at near room temperature [22].

At the elevated temperatures the kinetics of the leaching were expected to allow shorter contact times, therefore the 60 minutes and 24 hours experiments were considered only for the open system operating below the boiling point of the leaching agent. In summary, these selected temperatures and contact times allow to study the effect of these parameters on the leaching performance, while maintaining a clear link to realistic environmental exposure and time scales used in industrial metal recovery processes.

4.5 Potential implications for the leaching of specific elements and groups of elements

The effect of leaching medium, liquid-to-solid ratio, temperature and contact time leads to distinct leaching patterns for different elements:

- **Alkali and alkaline earth metals (Na, K, Ca, Mg)** - These elements are mainly associated with easily soluble salts and the amorphous part of the mineral matrix. Their release is usually rapid, dominated by simple dissolution, and is only moderately sensitive to pH, especially under near-neutral conditions [23].
- **Sulphur (S)** – In fly ash and biomass char, sulphur occurs primarily in the form of alkali and calcium sulphates (e.g., K_2SO_4 , Na_2SO_4 , $CaSO_4$) and, to a lesser extent, as metal sulphides. The sulphate fraction is usually easily leachable with water and dilute acids, so a significant portion of S can be removed already in the first leaching steps. pH primarily influences the solubility of calcium sulphate and the sorption of sulphates on mineral surfaces. Longer contact times and lower pH allow for additional oxidation of sulphides and an increase in the total S charge in solution [24].
- **Phosphorus (P)** – In mineral materials, P usually occurs in the form of sparingly soluble calcium and magnesium phosphates and in phases bound to Al and Fe. For this reason, phosphorus leaching in water is low, but it increases significantly in acidic environments and in the presence of complexing ligands (e.g., citric acid, EDTA), which can destabilize Ca phosphates or disrupt P-Fe/Al bonds. At higher pH, P occurs in the form of anions (HPO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-}), the mobility of which is strongly controlled by sorption on Fe/Al oxides and hydroxides [9].

- **Chloride (Cl)** - Chlorine contained in ash and char is mainly present in the form of highly soluble chlorides such as NaCl, KCl, and CaCl₂. These phases dissolve very quickly when the material comes into contact with water, so chloride leaching is mainly controlled by the liquid-to-solid ratio and the number of rinsing stages, rather than by pH. Many studies have shown that one or more stages of water leaching can remove most of the chlorides from char, ash and biomass, which is important both for reducing salinity and for limiting the risk of corrosion when such materials are used in structural applications [25].
- **Transition and heavy metals (e.g. Zn, Cu, Pb, Cd, Cr, Ni)** - Their leaching is strongly dependent on pH, complexation, and redox conditions. Lowering the pH usually increases their solubility and leaching from coal fly ash, while a high final pH in the leachate can significantly reduce their mobility. Complexing agents can further enhance their release [13].
- **Oxyanion-forming elements (e.g. As, Se, Mo, Cr(VI))** - Their behaviour is less dependent on the solubility of simple salts and more on adsorption-desorption and redox conditions. Changes in pH, redox conditions, or the presence of competing anions can significantly modify their leaching behaviour, even with a constant mass composition [23];
- **Fly ash and biomass char** – In thermally treated materials, elements bound to soluble mineral phases are released rapidly during short contact times, while those contained in more stable minerals or in the carbon matrix are leached more slowly, often under diffusion control [18].

Overall, these trends confirm that the leaching process cannot be interpreted using a single parameter. A reliable assessment of environmental risk or metal recovery potential requires a combined assessment of the leaching environment, L/S ratio, temperature, and contact time for the individual element groups present in the material.

4.6 Basis for the selection of leaching conditions in this work

The leaching conditions used in this study were selected to reflect both environmentally relevant aspects and the most efficient metal leaching and, at a later stage, recovery.

First, water as the most neutral and abundantly available leaching medium was selected. As shown above, many char and ash constituents are (partly) soluble in water, which makes it a logical choice to start with this leaching agent before moving on to more aggressive and also more expensive chemicals. Then, to also address the recovery of non-water-soluble elements, additionally acidic, alkaline, and complexing solutions were introduced to investigate more aggressive conditions and metal recovery potential. When choosing the leaching agents, a long-term goal of closing the loop was kept in mind, here meaning that in the optimal case the leaching agents should be recovered and reused after the leaching. This aspect will be investigated later during this project, namely in WP8.2 *Leaching conditions validation*.

Second, the liquid-to-solid ratio (expressed in grams of the leaching solution per grams of dry mass of the substrate) was set at 5, 10, and 20. A ratio of 10 was considered the reference value at which representative mobile fraction leaching could be achieved with a practical leachate volume. A factor of 5 reflects water-limited conditions and is suitable for identifying readily soluble fractions, while 20 represents a high-leaching scenario, used to approximate the upper range of elemental mobility.

Third, contact times of 1, 5, 60 minutes, and 24 hours were chosen to account for both a rapid initial leaching stage and near-steady-state conditions. 1 and 5 minutes reflect the immediate leaching of surface-bound and readily soluble substances, 60 minutes represents an intermediate timescale relevant to technical mixing and/or reactor residence time, and 24 hours provides a near-equilibrium reference point for comparing different systems.

Ultimately, for the initial screening at the laboratory scale a relatively wide range of temperatures was chosen in order to evaluate both the conditions applicable in an “open” system, that is with a minimum evaporation of the leaching agent (25°C and 60°C), as well as the more aggressive conditions, with temperatures up to 200°C using a pressure reactor and an automated Advanced Solvent Extraction (ASE) system.

Table 4. An overview of the leaching parameters and leaching systems applied during the experimental work described in this report.

Leaching parameter	Open batch system <i>in vitro</i> (BiV)	Pressure reactor (PR)	Advanced Solvent Extraction (ASE)
Leaching agent	water, HCl, CA, OA, AA, NaOH, EDTA, H ₂ O ₂	water	water
Leaching ratio (L/S)	5, 10, 20	10	5, 10, 20
Leaching time	1, 5, 60 minutes 24 hours	60, 120 minutes	5 minutes
Leaching temperature	25°C, 60°C	60°C, 120°C, 160°C	25°C, 60°C, 200°C
Leaching pressure	ambient	ambient, 10 bar, 20 bar	110 bar
Report chapter	5	6	7

Table 4 shows an overview of the leaching parameters and leaching systems applied during the experimental work described in this report, also highlighting the respective report sections describing each system. Together, these parameters define an experimental setup that allows the evaluation of the mobility of different element groups under realistic and intensive conditions, and also supports the assessment of both the environmental behaviour and the leaching and recovery potential of selected metals from the studied biomass chars.

4.7 Envisaged leaching strategies

The valuable elements of interest are present in the gasification residues in different forms. The most suitable recovery strategy will strongly depend on the arrangement and the arrangement of these elements of interest in the solid material. To illustrate this idea, different arrangements are shown in **Figure 3**.

Figure 3. Two possible different arrangements of valuable components of interest (red dots) in a gasification residue matrix (black dots): component relatively easily accessible to extraction agents (left); component encapsulated in the residue matrix and therefore not easily accessible (right). [Source: RIC]

Considering the above, different possible recovery pathways could be imagined:

1. Separate individual elements, starting from the most abundant one;
2. Selectively separate compounds of interest from a larger matrix (“cherry-picking”).

The first approach would gradually remove the bulk compound(s), consequently increasing the relative share of the elements present in smaller quantities. It could also make these less abundant compounds more accessible for recovery. Also, for the second approach it is necessary to make the specific elements accessible for recovery, but this could be done in a different way, e.g. by breaking up the bulk structure. A schematic representation of both approaches is shown in **Figure 4**.

Figure 4. Increasing the accessibility of valuable components for recovery: by removing the bulk compound(s) (left); by breaking up the structure of the bulk (right). [Source: RIC]

5 Leaching experiments - Batch experiments *in vitro*

5.1 Methodology

Batch-mode *in vitro* (BiV) leaching experiments were carried out under controlled laboratory conditions to evaluate the mobility and release behaviour of chemical components from char samples derived from different types of biomass, as well as from Miscanthus ash. The main objective was to compare the leaching efficiency of various materials and to assess the influence of leaching medium composition, process temperature, as well as the contact time and the leaching sequence on the extraction of inorganic components.

The char used for the leaching experiments was produced from raw biomass at 550°C under pyrolysis conditions in a laboratory batch pyrolysis/gasification setup at RIC. The details of this setup and the char production process are described in Deliverable D7.3 [6]. Miscanthus ash was obtained during the actual biomass gasification process of seed-based hybrids Miscanthus blend and was collected from the second cyclone after the gasifier during the experiments performed within the MISCOMAR+ project; a detailed description of these experiments can be found in the related report [26].

This comparative approach was chosen to enable the identification of differences in chemical stability and solubility of the investigated matrices, and to provide insights into the environmental behaviour and potential recovery of key elements from chars produced from distinct biomass feedstocks.

Based on the analysis presented in Section 4, the following operational parameters were chosen:

- Leaching media - a range of extraction agents representing different chemical environments (neutral, acidic, alkaline, complexing, and oxidizing) was selected. The following reagents were used:
 - distilled water (H₂O);
 - Ammonium acetate (CH₃COONH₄, 1 mol/L);
 - Hydrochloric acid (HCl, 1 mol/L);
 - Citric acid (C₆H₈O₇, 0.5 mol/L);
 - Sodium hydroxide (NaOH, 0.5 mol/L);
 - Oxalic acid (C₂H₂O₄, 0.5 mol/L);
 - Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA, 0.1 mol/L);
 - Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂, 5 mol/L);
- Temperature: 25°C and 60°C;
- Liquid-to-solid ratio (L/S): 5:1, 10:1, 20:1 (w/w);
- Leaching durations: 5 minutes, 1 hour, and 24 hours;
- Additional variants: some experiments were conducted both with and without ultrasonic assistance, to evaluate the effect of sonication on extraction efficiency and potential enhancement of mass transfer.

All reagents listed above were of *pro analyse* grade. The desired concentrations were obtained by preparing appropriate dilutions from concentrated liquids, or from solids.

The procedure for preparing samples for leaching consisted of accurately weighing the vessel on an analytical balance (Radwag AS 220.3Y), then weighing the char/ash with an accuracy of 0.0001 g into this vessel. A reagent was added to the prepared sample in the appropriate weight ratio, weighed on a technical balance (Radwag WLC 6/A2/C/2) with an accuracy of 0.01 g. The vessel with the sample was then placed on a magnetic stirrer as quickly as possible. All leaching experiments were performed using magnetic stirrers with a heated platform (Steinberg Systems SBS-MR-1600/1T PRO). The stirring speed was maintained at 300 RPM, while the temperature was controlled by a built-in thermocouple sensor and a controller integrated into the stirring system.

A multi-step leaching procedure was applied for each time variant:

- For the 5-minute and 1-hour experiments, five consecutive leaching steps were conducted, corresponding to total contact times of 25 minutes and 5 hours, respectively;
- For the 24-hour leaching variant, two sequential steps were performed, providing a total exposure time of 48 hours.

In these experiments all steps involved leaching with water. Furthermore, a series of two-step leaching experiments were carried out to investigate the leaching performance of leaching agents other than water as well as the sequential extraction behaviour of the different elements. The first leaching step (1:10 ratio, 1 h, 25°C) was performed using distilled water and a sufficiently large sample volume to ensure repeatability across all subsequent analyses. The second leaching step was conducted using the following solutions: distilled water, ammonium acetate, hydrochloric acid, citric acid, sodium hydroxide, oxalic acid, EDTA, and hydrogen peroxide. Additionally, for the leaching variant with ammonium acetate, a third step using hydrochloric acid was included, as suggested by relevant literature, to evaluate potential changes in element mobility under acidic conditions following complexing extraction [27]. The investigated leaching sequences are schematically presented in Figure 5. Figure 6 of the base-case batch leaching set-up, shows a beaker with char suspended in leaching solution and the subsequent filtration of the leachate for analysis.

Figure 5. Leaching sequences scheme. [Source: RIC]

Figure 6. Batch leaching setup. [Source: RIC]

After each leaching step, the following procedure was applied:

1. Solid–liquid separation: the suspension was filtered under vacuum using 0.45 µm membrane filters (Whatman ME25/21 ST, diameter 47 mm);
2. Filtrate handling: the obtained filtrate was collected and preserved for further analysis. Determination of selected elements and ions was performed using HACH cuvette tests, which was the primary analytical method applied for the analysis of the leachate. The following elements were measured: potassium, lead, phosphorus, sulphur, magnesium, zinc, iron, silicon, and nitrogen. Selected leachate samples were analysed by ICP-OES in order to cross-check the cuvette test results and extend the analytical scope;
3. The solid residue remaining on the filter was dried in a laboratory oven at 105°C for 24 hours. After drying the solids were separated from the filter for weighing, a portion of the material was subjected to CHS elemental analysis and ICP-OES determination to assess the residual composition. The remaining part of the sample was used for subsequent leaching experiments, allowing for comparative assessment of element mobility under different extraction conditions.

All experiments were performed under strictly controlled conditions to ensure reproducibility and comparability across all samples and leaching variants. All glassware and vessels used in the leaching experiments were thoroughly washed with ultrapure water and heated in a laboratory oven (Memmert UF110) at 105°C to remove any residual impurities and ensure complete dryness prior to use.

For each series of analyses, blank samples were also prepared to assess potential interferences from the reagents and solution matrix used. For each cuvette test, a separate blank sample was prepared using the relevant reagents and deionized water to determine any background signal resulting from the test itself or side reactions. The blank values obtained were then subtracted from the results measured in the leached solutions, which made it possible to eliminate “artificial” overestimation of concentrations. In several cases, it was observed that some leaching reagents reacted with the cuvette test reagents, causing discoloration or a change in colour intensity, which would likely result in a significant bias of the result. Samples in which this type of interference was found were excluded from further analysis and their results were considered unreliable. As a result, the analytical data obtained reflect the actual concentrations of the measured elements in the leached solutions.

In addition, leaching tests were made using ultrasound to see if acoustic energy could make the process more efficient in terms of the recovery of the elements, and possibly allow the reduction of the leaching time. In this approach, instead of a magnetic stirrer, a Polsonic SONIC 10 ultrasonic cleaner operating at a constant frequency of 40 kHz was used. Ultrasound can promote the breakdown of agglomerates, improve contact between the solid phase and the solution, and increase the release of minerals from the porous structure of the sample, making this technique potentially beneficial for intensifying the leaching process.

All experimental data, including experimental conditions, reagents and analytical results from the cuvette tests were continuously stored in an Excel file. Each experiment was given a unique identifier which was later used to identify both solid and liquid samples related to this experiment. The results from other analytical methods, mainly ICP-OES were stored in a separate Excel file. All results were imported into an MS Access database dedicated to this research work.

5.2 Results

5.2.1 Methodology of calculations and blank measurements

The main aim of the analysis of the results obtained during the experiments was to assess the effectiveness of the leaching process, at this stage mainly by comparing the influence of the different leaching parameters on the separation of different elements from the solid substrate (char or ash). The key parameter was called the “recovered fraction” and was meant to indicate the percentage of a specific element that was transferred from the char to the leachate. In general, the recovered fraction of an element i could be expressed as

$$\text{Recovered fraction of element } i (RF_i) = \frac{m_{i, \text{extracted}}}{m_{i, \text{raw char}}} \cdot 100\%$$

The calculation of the mass of the element i in the raw char is straightforward, based on the mass of the raw char and the concentration of the element i in the char (see Section 3.2). The calculation of the mass of the extracted element can be done in two different ways:

- the “direct” method, using the concentrations of the element i in the leachate and the mass of the leachate;
- the “left-in-char” (LiC) method, using the concentrations of the element i left in the char after a leaching step.

The respective equations are as follows:

$$RF_{i,direct} = \frac{C_{i,leachate} \cdot m_{leachate}}{m_{i,raw\ char}} \cdot 100\%$$

$$RF_{i,LiC} = \frac{m_{i,raw\ char} - m_{i,leached\ char}}{m_{i,raw\ char}} \cdot 100\% = \left(1 - \frac{m_{i,leached\ char}}{m_{i,raw\ char}}\right) \cdot 100\%$$

The direct RF_i was used in all experiments, while the RF_i based on the LiC was used only in the selected experiments, where char samples were sent to ICP analysis after the leaching. An overview of these results is given in **Table 5**. The values of RF_i calculated directly and via the LiC method are redundant and were used to analyse the mass balance closure (see paragraph 0).

The values shown in Table 5 represent the concentrations detected in the blank solutions prepared for each leaching reagent. These results indicate the intrinsic background levels of selected ions originating from the reagents themselves, which were subsequently subtracted from all analytical measurements to avoid artificial overestimation of leached element concentrations. The blank data confirm that several reagents, particularly AA and NaOH, contribute measurable amounts of certain ions, underlining the need for blank correction in further calculations. Furthermore, for Mg there was an interaction between the sample and the reagents in the Mg cuvette test causing the discoloration of the liquid, which made the actual concentration measurement impossible.

Table 5. Blank measurements for all solutions used for all measured elements. Not measurable (n.m) - the measurement caused discoloration of the liquid, which made the actual concentration measurement impossible.

Elements/ Solution	Pb _{total} [mg/L]	SO ₄ [mg/L]	Mg _{total} [mg/L]	P _{total} [mg/L]	K _{total} [mg/L]	Zn _{total} [mg/L]	Fe ²⁺ [mg/L]	Fe _{total} [mg/L]	Fe ³⁺ [mg/L]
H ₂ O	0.097	10.6	0.038	0	0.122	0	0	0	0
AA, 1 mol/L	0.110	10.6	n.m.	0	1046	0	0	0	0
NaOH, 0.5 mol/L	0.449	133	22.1	0	0.194	0.117	0	0.016	0.016
HCl, 1 mol/L	0.098	10.6	n.m.	0	0	0.191	0	0	0
CA, 0.5 mol/L	0.166	10.6	0	0	0	0	0	0.024	0.024
OA, 0.5 mol/L	0.070	10.7	n.m.	0	0	0	0	0	0
EDTA, 0.1 mol/L	0.080	10.6	n.m.	0	0.055	0	0	0	0
H ₂ O ₂ , 5 mol/L	0.092	10.7	n.m.	0	2.33	0	0	0	0

5.2.2 Leaching ratio

In leaching processes, one of the key operating parameters is the liquid to solid ratio (L/S), which determines the amount of solvent (leaching agent) per unit mass of solid material to be leached. This parameter affects both the dissolution rate and the maximum possible yield of elements, which is determined by the solubility limits of the respective elements and compounds. Too little liquid can limit the mixing of the two streams and lead to solution saturation, while too much increases reagent consumption and product dilution, reducing process efficiency. Before starting the actual tests, three L/S ratios were selected (5:1, 10:1, and 20:1) on the basis of literature reports, as described in Section 4.3.

Figure 7 shows the effect of the L/S ratio on the yield of selected elements (K, S, P, Mg) from MMX Char leached with water at 25°C for 5 minutes.

Figure 7. Leaching ratio comparison for MMX Char at 25 °C and 5 min.

Increasing the L/S ratio from 5:1 to 20:1 led to an increase in the recovery of all analysed elements, but the extent of the changes varies significantly between them:

- The potassium (K) recovery increased from 26.0% at L/S = 5:1 to 34.8% at L/S = 20:1, which is a relative increase of ca. 25% and 34% when comparing to the lowest L/S. The sulphur (S) increased from 16.4% to 20% and then decreased back to 18.9%, meaning relative improvements of 22% and 15%, respectively. The absolute differences in RF values were relatively small, besides, the increasing trend (for K) seemed to flatten, suggesting that K and S have high solubility even at the lowest L/S ratio tested, and further dilution of the solution would bring only minor or no (for S at 20:1) benefits;
- Phosphorus (P) and magnesium (Mg) showed a significantly stronger dependence on the amount of liquid. Their recovery almost doubled when the amount of solution increased from 10:1 to 20:1 (P: 2.23% to 4.71%; Mg: 1.58% to 3.04%). This indicates that they occur in less soluble or more matrix-bound forms that require a larger volume of solution for effective release. Here, however, the RFs are small (<5%).

Although increasing the L/S ratio to 20:1 improved P and Mg recovery, later chapters will show that similar or even higher yields can be achieved by modifying other process parameters, such as temperature, reagent type, or phase contact time. This eliminates the need to use very high volumes of solvent, which would be uneconomical, especially when potentially scaling up the process to an industrial scale. For the experiments investigating other parameters, it was decided to use an L/S ratio of 10:1 at this stage.

5.2.3 Leaching time and temperature

5.2.3.1 Overall comparison

To evaluate how temperature and contact time affect the extraction efficiency of key water-soluble elements, a set of leaching experiments was performed for all four chars (MMX, CW, HAY, DW) and for MA ash. Each material was leached under four sets of process conditions combining two temperatures (25°C and 60°C) and two leaching times (5 and 60 minutes). For every solid, cumulative recovery profiles were obtained, showing the changes or contributions of each leaching step to the total recovered fraction of each analysed element. We collected data from each of the five steps. For the sake of clarity

in this discussion only two profiles are presented: after the first leaching step (representing fast, easily mobilised fractions) and after the fifth step (representing the total water-extractable fraction).

The aim was to develop general trends in element mobility and to determine which elements are most responsive to more intense process conditions. An important aspect was to find out if conditions that are more demanding (i.e., higher temperature, longer time) improve the degree of leaching enough to justify their use.

The leaching behaviour of MMX Char shown in Figure 8, confirms that potassium, sulphur and phosphorus dominate the water-soluble fraction. Significant amounts of potassium and sulphur are released already during the first leaching step, yielding RFs higher than 30% and nearly 20%, respectively. Increasing the temperature from 25°C to 60°C and extending the contact time from 5 to 60 minutes cause only minor improvements, confirming that easily soluble salts present in MMX Char dissolve rapidly and are only weakly affected by the increased leaching temperature and/or leaching time. Magnesium and lead showed lower overall recovery, but similarly remained only marginally sensitive to increased temperature or longer leaching. Overall, MMX Char contained a water-leachable fraction, which was released quickly, but clearly showed a release limit for each individual step. This, in fact, led to the observation that the release of individual elements into the solution is more affected by the number of the leaching steps, than by the temperature or the leaching time. After 5 leaching steps the RF of K reaches around 80%, which approximately doubles the RF achieved in the first step. Similar behaviour can be observed for S, while for P this effect is even more pronounced and the RF after the 5th step is approximately 4 times higher than after Step 1. Nonetheless it is clear that only 20% of the P present in the raw material can be recovered by water leaching. For the metals this fraction is even lower, but this can be considered as an advantage, especially regarding the heavy metals Zn and Pb.

Figure 8. MMX Char – comparison of element recovery after Step 1 and Step 5 under different time and temperature conditions.

Figure 9 shows that for CW char the step wise water leaching results in a clear hierarchy in element mobility. Potassium and sulphur are the most mobile species, but they respond differently to time and temperature. After the first leaching step, K reaches about 18–20% recovery under three of the four conditions, while the most intensive case (60°C, 60 min) gives roughly twice this value. After five steps, all conditions converge to total K recoveries of about 60–70%; only the combination of 25°C and 60 min remains visibly lower (about 30%). This indicates that higher temperature and longer contact time mainly accelerates the initial release of K, whereas the overall water-soluble K pool in CW is moderate.

Sulphur is leached even more efficiently. Already in Step 1 the recovered fraction is around 5–20 %, and after Step 5 it increases to approximately 60–80 %, with higher temperature and short time giving the highest values. Phosphorus shows a different pattern: first-step recoveries are modest but clearly detectable (around 5–8 %), and the cumulative recovery after five steps rises only to about 10–15 %, with limited differences between conditions. Magnesium is the least mobile of the major elements, with recovered fractions below about 2 % after Step 1 and only 3–5 % after Step 5, almost independent of time and temperature. For zinc and lead the recovered fraction is 0 %, which is consistent with the fact that these elements were not detected in the raw CW char.

Overall, CW Char exhibits very efficient water leaching of S and K and only weak mobilisation of P and Mg, while trace metals stay largely immobile.

When compared with MMX Char, several differences become apparent. MMX contains a larger water-soluble pool of K and P: its K recovery reaches ~80% and P ~20% after five steps, whereas CW levels off at ~35–70% for K and 10–15% for P. At the same time, CW leaches S more effectively than MMX, achieving higher final recoveries and a stronger response to process intensification. For P, CW shows higher recovered fractions already after the first step, but MMX overtakes it after multiple steps, indicating a larger slowly dissolving P fraction in MMX. In both chars, Mg and heavy metals (for MMX) remain only weakly water-soluble, which is favourable from an environmental perspective and motivates the use of more selective reagents in subsequent leaching stages.

Figure 9. CW Char – comparison of element recovery after Step 1 and Step 5 under different time and temperature conditions.

The RF results for HAY char are shown in **Figure 10**, again showing a clear dominance of potassium and sulphur in the dissolved fraction. After Step 1, K already reaches relatively high recovered fractions of about 28–50%, with the highest values at 60°C and 60 min. After Step 5, the total K recovery increases further to roughly 80–90% for all conditions, and the spread between the different time–temperature combinations becomes small (about 10%). This indicates that the bulk of water-soluble K in HAY is released quickly, while successive steps mainly complete the dissolution of the same phases.

Sulphur is also efficiently leached. Its RF after Step 1 is around 30%, and increases to approximately 40–50% after Step 5, with the more intensive conditions (60 °C, 60 min) giving the highest values. Thus, both temperature and longer contact time have a visible, positive effect on S release.

Phosphorus remains only moderately soluble: Step-1 RFs are of the order of 2–4%, and the cumulative recovery after five steps reaches about 8–9%, with limited dependence on temperature or time. Magnesium with zero RFs after Step 1 and total recoveries RFs stay zero too under all conditions. Zinc is present in the raw HAY char, its water-leachable fraction is very small, so RFs stay about 1-3% after Step 5. For lead, the recovered fraction is 0 %, which is consistent with the fact that Pb was not detected in the raw HAY char.

In comparison with MMX Char, HAY exhibits a similar qualitative pattern – potassium and sulphur dominate the water-soluble fraction, whereas P, Mg, Zn and Pb remain largely in the solid phase – but the overall water recoveries of K and S are higher in HAY and the effect of temperature is more visible. For phosphorus, both chars show low total RFs, confirming that most P remains in forms that cannot be removed by only water leaching.

Figure 10. HAY Char – comparison of element recovery after Step 1 and Step 5 under different time and temperature conditions.

The RF results for DW Char are shown in **Figure 11**. Sulphur clearly dominates the water-leachable fraction. After Step 1, S reaches recovered fractions of roughly 30–60 %, depending on the time–temperature combination. By Step 5 these values increase to about 60–80 %. For the mildest conditions (25 °C, 5 min) the RF of S rises from ~30 % to ~60 %, i.e. by about 30 percentage points, which corresponds to an approximately twofold increase. The other conditions show slightly smaller but still pronounced increases. Overall, the trend consistently indicates that higher temperature and longer leaching time enhance S release from DW Char, and the effect of process intensification on S is stronger here than for the other chars.

Potassium behaves differently. In Step 1 its RF is relatively low (around 2–25 %), and there is a clear gap between the most intensive conditions (60 °C, 60 min) and the remaining three cases. After Step 5, K recovery increases to about 25–45 %, with the highest value again at 60 °C and 60 min. Thus, time and temperature noticeably improve K leaching, but the final K RF remains the lowest of all four chars, indicating a comparatively small water-soluble K pool in DW.

Magnesium and phosphorus remain weakly soluble. Their RFs after Step 1 are close to 1 %, and even after steps 5 they reach only about 2–5 % (Mg) and up to ~5 % (P). When DW is compared with CW (both woody chars), the RF of Mg is similar, but the RF of P is clearly lower for DW (maximum ~5 %) than for CW (up to ~18 %), which suggests a different occurrence or binding form of phosphorus in these two materials.

A notable feature of DW Char is the appearance of measurable zinc in the leachate. Although RFs remain about 7–12 % after Step 5, Zn shows the same qualitative pattern as other moderately soluble components, with slightly higher recoveries at elevated temperature and longer time. Lead was not detected in the raw DW Char, so its recovered fraction in all water-leaching tests is, by definition, 0 %. Overall, DW Char demonstrates that sulphur is by far the most mobile component, while potassium, magnesium, phosphorus and zinc exhibit limited but clearly measurable sensitivity to increasing leaching time and temperature.

Figure 11. DW Char – comparison of element recovery after Step 1 and Step 5 under different time and temperature conditions.

The RF results for MA Ash are shown in Figure 12. In this case the highest recovery of dissolved components among all analysed materials is observed, which is expected for a largely inorganic solid with a much lower carbon content than the char. Potassium is removed very effectively: after the first step the recovery reaches about 25–30% at room temperature and 65–70% at higher temperature, and these values show only minimal dependence on the contact time. After five steps the recovery increases to roughly 50% at room temperature and reaches almost 100% at higher temperature, making potassium the most easily leached component of the ash.

For the sulphur similar RF values as for potassium were reached at 25°C. At 60°C the RFs decrease sharply, obtaining a maximum RF of around 10%. This is the opposite behaviour than in the case of potassium, where the temperature had a clearly positive effect on the RF. At this moment no clear explanation of this behaviour can be given. One of the hypotheses can be the release of gaseous sulphur compounds (e.g. SO₂, H₂S), but this was not measured nor observed organoleptically (smell), similar RF values. After five steps the recovery of sulphur is close to 55% for tested conditions in 25°C. Phosphorus remains only slightly soluble, with a maximum recovery of around 5% in Step 5, and its behaviour does not vary between different temperatures or times. Magnesium shows very limited solubility: at room temperature it increases only slightly between Step 1 and Step 5, while at higher temperature it is not leached at all. The RFs of zinc and lead are negligible.

In summary, the experiments with the MMX Ash demonstrated that at suitable temperatures water 100% RF of potassium can be reached. The maximum obtained RFs for sulphur were around 55%, but these values were achieved at the lower leaching temperature. Phosphorus, magnesium and trace metals remain in forms that barely dissolve in water under the tested conditions.

Figure 12. MA Ash – comparison of element recovery after Step 1 and Step 5 under different time and temperature conditions.

A comparison of all investigated materials clearly shows that the most leachable solid is MMX Ash, which results from its mainly inorganic nature and the absence of a dominating carbon matrix. Multistep water leaching efficiently removes a substantial fraction of easily soluble salts, primarily potassium and sulphur and, under more intensive conditions, also part of the water-soluble magnesium and phosphorus. For the chars (MMX, CW, HAY, DW), the overall recoveries are lower, although the elemental pattern remains similar: water preferentially extracts potassium and sulphur, while phosphorus, magnesium, zinc and lead largely remain in less soluble forms within the solid structure.

Across all materials, the first leaching step always contributes a major share of the water-extractable fraction, especially for K and, in some cases, S. However, the next steps have a significant impact on the overall RF. For several chars the cumulative RF increases markedly between Step 1 and Step 5 – for example, sulphur in DW Char roughly doubles its recovery, and phosphorus in MMX Char increases by a factor of about four. This shows that repeated water contact is required to access more slowly dissolving salt phases, internal porosity and partially trapped solution.

In practical terms, multistep water leaching can therefore be regarded as an effective pre-treatment, removing most of the highly mobile, easily soluble components (mainly potassium salts and a large share of sulphates), but also a measurable portion of the more slowly leachable phosphorus and magnesium. After this stage, the remaining solid is depleted in simple salts and enriched in less mobile

species, which makes it better suited for subsequent, more selective leaching with dedicated reagents (acids, bases or complexing agents) aimed at targeted recovery of specific elements.

Table 6. A summary of the maximum recovery fractions (RFs) achieved during the water leaching experiments at 25°C and 60°C, and the leaching times of 5 and 60 minutes, after 5 leaching steps. The values between brackets indicate the RF after the first step.

	K	S	P	Mg	Zn	Pb
CW	71 (38) 60°C, 60 m	81 (7) 60°C, 5 m	18 (9) 60°C, 60 m	4 (2) 60°C, 5 m		
DW	45 (25) 60°C, 60 m	79 (58) 60°C, 60 m	4 (2) 60°C, 60 m	5 (2) 60°C, 60 m	14 (0) 60°C, 60 m	
MMX	83 (43) 60°C, 60 m	43 (22) 25°C ¹⁾ , 60 m	19 (3) 25°C, 60 m	4 (1) 60°C, 60 m		2 (0) 60°C, 5 m
HAY	94 (53) 60°C, 60 m	51 (34) 60°C, 60 m	9 (3) 60°C, 60 m		4 (3) 25°C, 5 m	
MA	112 (71) 60°C, 60 m	57 (17) 25°C, 5 m	5 (0) 25°C, 5 m	3 (2) 25°C, 60 m		
Notes: ¹⁾ the value is just minimally higher than the result at 60°C and 5 minutes						

5.2.3.2 Step-by-step comparison – water leaching

To better compare the kinetic tests with the multi-step leaching series, the water-leaching results were re-plotted as cumulative recovered fractions of individual elements versus total exposure time. For each material, the curves combine data from three experimental series: five 1-minute steps (total 5 min), five 5-minute steps (25 min) and five 60-minute steps (300 min). In this way, short single-step tests and the longer multi-step leaching can be evaluated on a common time axis.

Figure 13 (left) combines K and Mg. Here, the points from the short steps tests (5 × 1 min and 5 × 5 min) and from the longer steps tests (5 × 60 min, i.e. up to a total contact time of 300 min) fall on an almost continuous trend. For K, the recovered fraction increases from about 15 % after 1 minute to almost 80 % after the 25- and 300-min contact time, confirming that most of the water-soluble K is released rapidly and that further leaching mainly completes the dissolution of the same salt phases. Magnesium follows the same pattern but at much lower levels, reaching only about 5 % in total. This indicates that Mg occurs in less soluble forms, although its release is still controlled by one relatively simple mechanism. For these elements (K and Mg), it is worth noting that the results are practically identical for five 1-minute steps and one 5-minute step.

In contrast, the behaviour of S, P, and Pb (**Figure 13**, right) is less uniform. The sulphur content increases with exposure time and reaches over 40% recovery, but the transition between short time tests and the multi-step series is less smooth than for K. In the 5 steps of each series, there is only about a 5% difference between the times, in advantage of the longest time. This may suggest that slower dissolving sulphate phases may leach out over a longer period of time.

The cumulative recovery for phosphorus and lead is less than ~20% for P and less than ~3% for Pb, and their curves show visible shifts between short-term and multi-stage data. It is important to note that for 5 min and 60 min, we obtain the same values for both elements after the first step. Only over time is the phosphorus increase significantly higher. On this basis, it can be concluded that P and Pb in MMX Char occur in several mineral forms with different reactivity, and later stages of leaching provide access to fractions that are not available during short tests.

Figure 13. MMX Char – Effect of leaching time on RF.

For CW Char, the time-dependent water-leaching behaviour was evaluated for four elements: K, S, P and Mg (Zn and Pb were not detected in the raw char and are therefore not shown). The data combine results from leaching sequences consisting of five 5-min steps (total 25 min) and five 60-min steps (total 300 min), and are plotted as cumulative recovered fractions versus total exposure time (Figure 14).

Figure 14. CW Char – Effect of the leaching time on the RF of the selected elements.

Figure 15. HAY Char – Effect of the leaching time on the RF of the selected elements.

Figure 16. DW Char – Effect of the leaching time on the RF of the selected elements.

Figure 17. MA – Effect of the leaching time on the RF of the selected elements.

5.2.4 Reagent sequences

5.2.4.1 2nd step after water leaching

After the initial water leaching step (1 h, 25 °C), the second-step experiments were carried out with different leaching media. In this section, only ICP-OES (VTT) data for the leached liquid are presented because the cuvette method is not suitable for coloured or strongly absorbing solutions and would have cross-sensitivity with most reagents other than water.

For K Figure 18 (left) shows that the most efficient second-step extractant is clearly 1 M AA, giving recovered fractions of around 55–70% for the HAY and MMX chars and about 50–55 % for DW. 1 M HCl and 5 M H₂O₂ also leach substantial additional K (up to ~50% for HAY and MMX), while 0.5 M NaOH is particularly effective for DW. In contrast, OA removes only a small fraction of K from HAY and MMX. Overall, AA provides a strong, relatively selective K extraction, especially for the HAY and MMX chars.

Sulphur shows in Figure 18 (right), a different pattern: the highest additional recovery is obtained with 1 M AA, in particular for the DW char, where the recovered fraction approaches 70%. HAY and MMX also respond well to AA (around 30–40%), while CW remains at a lower but fairly constant level across all reagents. Oxalic acid and HCl give moderate S leaching, where a NaOH has no clear advantage over the organic acids. This suggests that AA is the most suitable second step when simultaneous removal of K and S is desired, especially from DW.

Figure 18. Recovered fraction of K (left) and S (right) in the second leaching step for all biomass chars (CW, DW, HAY, MMX) using different leaching media.

For P shows in Figure 19 (left), 1 M HCl is overall the most effective medium, with recovered fractions up to about 50% for MMX and ~35% for HAY; it also gives the highest recovery among the reagents tested for CW. Among the organic acids, 0.5 M citric acid (CA) and 0.5M oxalic acid (OA) are also efficient, particularly for MMX, where CA reaches ~45 % and OA ~35%. In contrast, NaOH is generally ineffective for P, especially in DW and HAY, where almost no additional P is released. Across all leaching media, MMX consistently shows the highest recovered fraction of P, indicating that P in this char is present in more acid-soluble forms than in the other materials. These trends indicate that acidic media provide the best second-step leaching of P, with HCl maximising extraction and CA/OA offering slightly milder, more selective conditions.

For Zn shows in Figure 19 (right), the element is mainly mobilised from the DW, HAY and MMX chars, with only very minor release from CW, which is consistent with the low Zn content in the original material. The strongest additional extraction is achieved with 1M HCl, where recovered fractions reach ~45–50% for DW and MMX and ~35% for HAY. High recoveries are also obtained with 0.5M oxalic acid (OA) and 0.5M citric acid (CA), especially for DW (around 40%) and for HAY/MMX (20–30%). EDTA leaches Zn efficiently from DW and MMX, whereas NaOH and AA are much less effective, particularly for HAY and MMX. Thus, Zn is best targeted in the second step by acidic or complexing reagents, with HCl providing the highest recovery and CA/OA offering better compromise options.

Figure 19. Recovered fraction of P (left) and Zn (right) in the second leaching step for all biomass chars (CW, DW, HAY, MMX) using different leaching media.

For Mg Figure 20 (left) shows that the recovered fractions are generally low but demonstrate a systematic response to the choice of leaching medium. The most efficient reagent is HCl, especially for HAY and MMX, where about 20–23% of Mg is additionally leached. CA and OA provide moderate extraction for these chars (up to ~15–16% for MMX and about 9–10% for HAY), whereas CW and DW show only a few percent Mg release in any medium. NaOH is essentially ineffective, and AA gives only minor additional leaching. This pattern indicates that Mg is largely associated with acid-soluble mineral phases in chars, and that an HCl step is required if significant Mg removal is targeted.

For Pb Figure 20 (right), shows that significant leaching is observed only for the MMX char. For the other chars the recovered fraction remains below the detection limit in the second step. For MMX - CA and HCl are the only media that show a notable effect, reaching ~30% and nearly 40% Pb recovery, respectively. This suggests that Pb in MMX is present in forms susceptible to complexation by citric acid and to dissolution in strong acid, while the other chars either contain much less Pb or it is locked in more stable, non-leachable phases under the conditions tested.

Figure 20. Recovered fraction of Mg (left) and Pb (right) in the second leaching step for all biomass chars (CW, DW, HAY, MMX) using different leaching media.

For Ca Figure 21 (left) shows that the element is moderately to strongly mobilised by several reagents. HCl gives the highest recovered fractions, with ~40% for HAY, ~27% for MMX and about 16–17% for CW and DW. EDTA and CA also leach Ca efficiently, reaching roughly 18–25% for HAY and MMX and slightly lower values for CW and DW, whereas NaOH and OA play only a minor role. AA releases Ca at an intermediate level. These results suggest that Ca can be co-extracted with other alkaline-earth metals in an HCl step, or more selectively removed using EDTA/CA when strong acid is not desirable.

For Mn Figure 21 (right) shows that it behaves similarly to Ca and Mg but with more pronounced responses for HAY and MMX. The highest additional Mn recovery is obtained with HCl, reaching about 35% for HAY and ~29% for MMX (with ~5–7% for CW and DW). CA and OA also show substantial leaching (around 15–25% for HAY and MMX), while EDTA is somewhat less effective, although it still mobilises noticeable amounts of Mn from MMX. NaOH and H₂O₂ have only a minor influence for all chars. This indicates that Mn is mainly bound in acid-soluble oxide or carbonate phases and is efficiently released in the acidic second step, especially from the more mineral-rich chars.

Figure 21. Recovered fraction of Ca (left) and Mn (right) in the second leaching step for all biomass chars (CW, DW, HAY, MMX) using different leaching media.

For Fe Figure 22 (left) shows that the recovered fractions in the second leaching step are clearly highest for the HAY and MMX chars. In these materials, OA achieves recovery rates of about 16–19%, while HCl reaches roughly 23–29%. In contrast, CW and DW show only low Fe mobilisation in all media (generally below 10 %), suggesting that most of their iron remains in relatively stable forms under the tested conditions. The strong response to OA and HCl for HAY and MMX is consistent with dissolution and complexation of Fe oxides and other acid-soluble Fe phases.

For Al Figure 22 (right) shows that the behaviour is partly similar but with a stronger contribution from alkaline and complexing media. The highest recoveries are again observed for the HAY and MMX chars, where OA yields about 23–27% Al and HCl around 29–31%. The CW char shows a distinct maximum in 0.5 M NaOH, with a recovered fraction of about 30 %, indicating that a significant part of Al in this material is present in aluminosilicate phases susceptible to alkaline environment. DW exhibits only moderate Al mobilisation (up to ~5-10%), only for NaOH, OA and HCl. Overall, these patterns suggest that Al in the chars is partly acid-soluble and partly accessible to complex- or base-assisted dissolution, and that the choice between OA, HCl and NaOH in the second step can be used to tune Al co-leaching with Fe and other metals.

Figure 22. Recovered fraction of Fe (left) and Al (right) in the second leaching step for all biomass chars (CW, DW, HAY, MMX) using different leaching media.

In summary, the second leaching step after 1h water extraction at 25°C shows that the choice of reagent can be used to tune both the efficiency and selectivity of element removal from the different biomass chars. AA is particularly effective for K (and S), while most macro and trace metals (P, Mg, Ca, Mn, Fe, Al and Zn, as well as Pb in MMX) are mobilised most strongly in HCl. CA and OA provide a useful intermediate option, giving substantial recoveries of P, Zn, Ca, Mn, Fe and Al while being milder than HCl. NaOH and H₂O₂ play only a minor role in this step, with noticeable effects mainly for K, Zn for DW and Al in CW.

The HAY and MMX chars consistently show the highest recovered fractions for most elements, indicating a larger share of acid-soluble or easily complexed phases, while CW is generally poor in trace metals and DW stands out mainly for Zn and S. Overall, the results demonstrate that a water pre-leach followed by a carefully selected second reagent allows partial separation between alkali elements (K,

S) and multivalent metals (P-bearing species, Zn, Pb, Ca, Mn, Fe, Al), which is important both for environmental assessment and for designing recovery-oriented leaching sequences.

5.2.4.2 3-step sequence

The bar charts in Figure 23 show the cumulative recovered fractions of selected elements (K, S, P, Mg, Zn, Pb) from each biomass char (MMX, HAY, CW, DW) in a three-step leaching sequence: water (1 h, 25 °C), 1 M ammonium acetate (AA) (5min, 25 °C) and 1 M HCl (5min, 25 °C). The values are based on ICP-OES analyses of the leachates performed by VTT.

In the case of K and S, water and AA already remove a significant portion of the leachable pool. In all chars, the total K recovery reaches ~50–90%, with AA clearly dominating in the second step (especially in MMX, HAY, and DW). Sulphur is strongly mobilized in DW and HAY (up to ~80–85% combined), mainly by water and AA, while in the case of CW, the recovered S fraction is 0%, reflecting the fact that the sulphur content in the original CW char was below the detection limit.

For P and Mg, the water and AA stages contribute only minor amounts, with most of the recovery achieved in the HCl stage. This is particularly evident for MMX and HAY, where P is ~35–55% and Mg ~20–27%. For condensation water and dissolved water, the total recovered P and Mg fractions remain lower, reflecting both the chemical composition and the lower acid-soluble fraction.

Figure 23. Cumulative recovered fractions of selected elements from biomass chars in a three-step leaching scheme.

For Zn and Pb, the three-step sequence highlights significant differences between the chars, but interpretation is linked to their initial composition in Figure 24.

Zn is leached primarily from DW and MMX, with relatively small contributions from water and AA and a dominant HCl step (up to ~70% in DW and ~40% in MMX). HAY shows only moderate Zn recovery, while for CW, the recovered fraction is effectively 0%, consistent with the fact that Zn content was below the detection limit in the raw CW char.

Pb is significant only for MMX: it is the only char in which Pb was detected in the starting material, and the second/third leaching steps recover a significant portion of this pool (up to ~40–45% in the final HCl step). For CW, HAY, and DW, the Pb content in the raw char was below the detection limit, so the recovered fraction is by definition 0% within the analytical uncertainty.

Char ICP Results

Figure 24. Char ICP Results in raw chars.

A detailed mass balance of individual elements and interpretation of these trends are presented in the next chapter.

5.3 Mass balance analysis

5.3.1 Basic equations

Overall mass balance (MB) for a leaching step k can be defined as follows:

$$m_{c,k} + m_{liq,k} = m_{cl,k} + m_{lea,k} + m_{unk,k}$$

where the indices c , k , liq , cl , lea and unk refer respectively to char, step k , liquid, leachate and unknown.

Due to the relatively small observed mass transfer between the solid phase and the liquid phase, it can be assumed that

$$m_{lea,k} = m_{liq,k}$$

Elemental MB for a leaching step k and element i is defined as shown in the equations below.

Overall MB for an element i :

$$m_{c,k,i} + m_{liq,k,i} = m_{cl,k,i} + m_{lea,k,i} + m_{unk,k,i}$$

Assumptions:

$$m_{lea,k} = m_{liq,k}$$

$$m_{cl,k} = m_{c,k} \cdot \frac{m_{c,1}}{m_{c,k}}$$

Input mass of element i :

$$m_{c,k,i} = m_{c,k} \cdot z_{i,c}$$

where $z_{i,c}$ is the concentration of the element i in the raw char obtained by the ICP, CHS, XRF and other relevant analyses. The mass of the element i in the leachate is defined by:

$$m_{lea,k,i} = m_{lea,k} \cdot x_{i,k}$$

where $x_{i,k}$ is the concentration of the element i in the leachate determined by the cuvette tests, titration or the ICP analysis. The mass of element i left in the char after the last step is defined by:

$$m_{cl,k,i} = \left(m_{c,1,i} - \sum_{n=1}^k m_{lea,n,i} - m_{err} \right) \cdot Z_{i,cl,k}$$

Finally, the elemental MB closure of the element i for the entire leaching sequence is given by:

$$\Delta m_{k,i} = m_{c,1,i} - m_{cl,k,i} - \sum_{n=1}^k m_{lea,n,i}$$

5.3.2 Per-step mass balance

The most comprehensive dataset was obtained for the experiments 17 and 30, involving MMX and CW char, respectively. These experiments consisted of three leaching steps, first being water leaching, followed by AA in step 2 and HCl in step 3. The dataset consisted of:

- elemental composition of the raw char – ICP and CHS;
- elemental composition of the char after each leaching step – ICP and CHS;
- elemental composition of the leachate after each leaching step – ICP and CT.

The data analysis presented in the next sections is focused on the trace elements, and to achieve the best comparison only the ICP data are considered here, both for the char as for the leachate. As the raw char was analysed at multiple laboratories, as described in Section 3.2, and the char after leaching from these experiments was analysed only at one laboratory (IL), also the analytical results related to the raw char were taken from this laboratory (IL), even despite the fact, that they deviated significantly from the results obtained by the other laboratories. It is assumed that as the analytical procedure was the same at a single laboratory, the results will have similar errors and therefore their comparison is justified, especially during the calculation of the recovered fraction (RF) via the Left-in-Char (LiC) route.

5.3.2.1 MMX char leaching (Experiment 17)

Figure 25 and Figure 26 present graphs showing the effect of different leaching media on the recovery of selected elements during the leaching of MMX, with parameters calculated via the Left-in-Char (LiC) route and the direct (leachate) route, respectively. In this analysis the calculation of the RF differs from the one shown in Section 5.2.1, as here each calculated RF refers to the input quantity of element i in the *particular step* and not in the raw char. In addition to the recovered fraction (RF), two additional parameters are shown: the absolute recovery, giving the mass of an element recovered per gram of total char input, and the normalized RF, where the normalization is done by selecting the highest RF in that dataset and dividing all other RFs by this maximum value.

The following observations and conclusions can be made regarding the dataset obtained in Experiment 17:

1. The RFs of Al, K, P, Ca and Mg (both except step 2), and Zn show nearly similar trends both via the LiC route and the leachate route, but the magnitudes are totally different, even up to two orders of the magnitude. For example, phosphorus (P) shows increasing RFs for the subsequent leaching steps, however the values calculated via the LiC route are 9.3%, 19.8% and 62.8%, while the calculation via the direct route yields 143%, 803% and 1745%, respectively. Nonetheless, the trend is the same in both cases ($RF_{step\ 1} > RF_{step\ 2} > RF_{step\ 3}$), eventhough the relative changes between the steps are again different. Once again it is stressed, that the char analysis used in these calculations gave the lowest concentrations of the individual elements, which is considered the reason for the RF calculated via the direct route to be over 100%.
2. All other analysed elements show different trends. The biggest differences include a very small amount of Ca being leached using AA according to the LiC method, while according to the leachate analysis the relative recovery is higher than in the case of water leaching. A similar trend can be observed for Mg, and this is noteworthy, since both metals belong to the same group of elements (alkaline earth metals) and often occur together in natural mineral matter (e.g. dolomite, magnesite). Fe is only detected in the leachate for HCl leaching, but LiC calculation suggests its decrease also during the use of other leaching agents.
3. Al concentration measured in the char after step 2 (AA leaching) is higher than in the raw material, which yields a negative recovery.
4. In terms of absolute values, LiC analysis shows Si as the element that is removed from the char in the highest amount, in the distance followed by K, Na and Ca. Leachate analysis points at K being present in the highest amount, followed by Ca and P (both during AN and HCl leaching).

5. Significant amounts of Si removed from the char in step 1 could indicate the presence of water-soluble Si compounds, being ortho-silicates, and specifically H_4SiO_4 . This is known to be formed at elevated temperatures (e.g. during the pyrolysis).
6. Normalized recovery values based on the LiC route show Si, K and P removed from the char in the highest shares during respectively Water, AA, and HCl leaching. The same analysis based on the direct route points at respectively K, P and again P;
7. For Al the LiC concentrations in the second step (AA leaching) was higher than in the input material, which yielded a negative RF value. Due to the limitation of the logarithmic scale this effect is only visible in the Normalised RF chart.

Figure 25. Graphs presenting the effect of different leaching media on the recovery of selected elements during the leaching of MMX (experiment 17), with parameters calculated via the Left-in-Char route: the recovered fraction (left), the absolute recovery (centre), normalized RF (right).

Figure 26. Graphs presenting the effect of different leaching media on the recovery of selected elements during the leaching of MMX (experiment 17), with parameters calculated via the direct (leachate) route: the recovered fraction (left), the absolute recovery (centre), normalized RF (right).

5.3.2.2 CW char leaching (Experiment 30)

Similarly to MMX discussed in the previous section, Figure 27 and Figure 28 present graphs showing the effect of different leaching media on the recovery of selected elements during the leaching of CW, with parameters calculated via the Left-in-Char (LiC) route and the direct (leachate) route, respectively.

The following observations and conclusions can be made regarding the dataset obtained in Experiment 30:

1. The RFs of Ca, Na and Zn show similar trends both calculated via the LiC route and the direct route. Contrary to MMX, the magnitudes of Ca recovery are in relatively good agreement, with water leaching (step 1) being very close (13.9 vs 12.8%) for both calculation routes. While promising, this has to be considered with care, however, taking into account the deviations and discrepancies for other elements, as well as the fact findings related to the ICP analysis of the char reported earlier and in D7.3.
2. The RF of Mg shows reasonable agreement between the LiC and the direct calculation, with the main difference being the leaching with AA: LiC route shows the lowest recovery, while the direct route yields a value between water and HCl. However, in this particular case the differences are small and possibly fall within the accuracy margin of the analyses.
3. K concentration measured in the char after step 1 is higher than in the raw material (!), which yields a negative recovery. Similar result is observed for Si, Al and Fe, all in step 2 (AA leaching). Furthermore, no S is detected in the leachate (values below LoQ).
4. All other analysed minerals show different trends and values for the LiC and the direct calculation routes of RF.
5. In terms of absolute values, LiC analysis returns Si as the element that is removed from the char in the highest amount (except for AA leaching (step 2), where the recovery is negative), in the distance (1 order of magnitude less) followed by Na and Ca. Leachate analysis points at K being present in the highest amount, followed by Ca.
6. Normalized RFs based on LiC calculation show Fe, K and Na removed from the char in the highest shares during respectively water, AA, and HCl leaching. The RF values based on the direct calculation point at P yielding the highest recovery for all leaching agents;
7. For K, Al and Fe the LiC concentrations in the respectively first and second step were higher than in the input material, which yielded negative RF values. Due to the limitation of the logarithmic scale this effect is only visible in the Normalised RF chart.

5.3.2.3 General remarks and conclusions

For both experiments 17 and 30 the following observations and conclusions can be made:

1. Raw measurement data do not allow the mass balance closure. The main reason for this is the analysis of the raw char and also of the intermediate char samples (between the subsequent leaching steps), as described in D7.3. The elemental matrix in these samples is dominated by the carbon, which makes the relative amounts of the inorganic elements to be very low, often in the ppm range. The uncertainties about the digestion procedure described in D7.3 add to the total uncertainty and the magnitude of the measurement error. During the analysis no element was identified that could act as a reliable "internal standard" to be used for the closure of the mass balance and for the use of data reconciliation techniques. Nonetheless a further investigation of this aspect is planned in the future work (WP8 Technology validation: SOEC and gasification residues recovery, T8.2 Leaching conditions validation).
2. It has to be taken into the account, that the leaching experiments discussed above investigated the sequential exposure of a char sample to different leaching agents. Therefore, the amount and also possibly the structure and the inorganic compounds present in the char in the consecutive leaching steps were different, and thus also the leaching efficiencies can be different. Nonetheless the relative recovery figures obtained via the LiC route as well as the leachate analysis route should be in agreement, which is not the case at the moment, as shown above.
3. Compared to the MMX experiment, the RMS deviation between the unit recovery (LiC - Leachate) is smaller for CW for all steps. This, however, can be partly influenced by the lower amounts of the individual elements in the CW ash. RMS of the differences between the relative recovery shows lower values for CW, which for steps 2 and 3 are ca. two times lower than these for MMX, while for step 1 the opposite is the case.

Figure 27. Graphs presenting the effect of different leaching media on the recovery of selected elements during the leaching of CW(experiment 30), with parameters calculated via the Left-in-Char route: the recovered fraction (left), the absolute recovery (center), normalized RF (right).

Figure 28. Graphs presenting the effect of different leaching media on the recovery of selected elements during the leaching of CW (experiment 30), with parameters calculated via the direct (leachate) route: the recovered fraction (left), the absolute recovery (center), normalized RF (right).

5.4 Other process parameters

In addition to the process parameters influencing the leaching process which were described in the previous sections, several additional parameters were investigated. The results of these investigations are described below.

5.4.1 Effect of leaching volume and stirring intensity

The effect of the leaching volume (with a constant L/S ratio) was investigated by comparing the results from experiment no. 11 performed in a 1 L beaker (the reference experiment) with two experiments (no. 24 and 25) performed in a 250 mL beaker, but using a bigger magnetic bar for the stirring. Therefore, it can be postulated that the relative stirring intensity was higher in experiments no. 24 and 25. The leaching temperature in these experiments was 60°C and the leaching time 60 minutes, and the substrate was the MMX char.

Figure 29 presents the comparison of the RFs of five elements (K, S, P, Mg, Pb) across the experiments no. 11, 24 and 25. At first it should be noticed that the experiments no. 24 and 25, i.e. with the higher relative stirring intensity yield reproducible result, which mutually differ by less than 5%, except for Mg (ca. 28% difference) and Pb (value below LoD in the experiment no. 24). Then it is clear, that the RF of potassium (K) is significantly higher in the experiments with the higher relative stirring intensity, achieving on average 59.5% recovery vs 42.7% (a relative increase of +39.3%) for the reference experiment. For sulphur (S) and phosphorus (P) also an increase was observed, but the absolute differences were much lower, with 20.95% average vs 18.8% in the reference experiment for S and 3.74% vs 3.03% for P. Still, the relative increase values for S and P were +11.4% and +23.4%, respectively. For Mg and Pb the differences are negative or uncertain, but these elements are also present in lower absolute quantities in the char, and also less prone to water leaching, as shown in the previous sections.

Higher relative stirring intensity suggests the possibility to increase the RF of K. In the biomass char, especially in the case of herbaceous biomass like MMX or HAY, this element is known to exist as KCl and deposited on the surface of the char particles. This could explain, why a more intense agitation helps to force this compound in the solution.

Figure 29. A comparison of the effect of the higher relative stirring intensity (experiments no. 24 and 25) vs the reference experiment (no. 11).

5.4.2 Effect of ultrasound

The application of ultrasound during the leaching experiments was postulated to have a positive effect on the leaching process and on the achieved RFs. Therefore a 5-step ultrasound-assisted water leaching experiment was performed, with Miscanthus Ash (MA) as the leached substrate. In this experiment the temperature was 25°C, and two leaching times (5 and 60 minutes) were tested. Ultrasound was applied by placing the beaker with the leaching agent in an ultrasonic bath (Polsonic SONIC-10) filled with water as the ultrasound transfer medium. In these experiments no mechanical stirring was applied. The results were compared to a reference experiment without the application of ultrasound (experiment no. 1), but with mechanical stirring.

Figure 30 and **Figure 31** show the comparison of the recovered fractions (RFs) of the selected elements achieved during the ultrasound-assisted leaching and the reference experiment, both of 5 minutes duration. The former figure shows the RFs achieved after the first leaching step (step 1), while the latter presents the cumulative results from steps 1 till 5, i.e. the total recovered fraction. In both cases it is clear that ultrasound-assisted leaching enabled a substantially higher potassium (K) recovery, while the effect on other elements was either counterproductive or negligible. It can also be concluded that the positive effect of the ultrasound on K recovery is primarily achieved in the first leaching step, as the difference between the ultrasound-assisted RF and the reference experiment barely increases when looking at step 1 and the cumulation after five steps (32.5 and 38.7%-points, respectively). This can be caused by the fact, that likely most of the water-leachable K-compounds have been removed in the final leaching steps, and therefore the leaching efficiency was diminishing from step to step. Similarly, to the effect of the stirring intensity described in the previous section, also here the high release of K species can be explained by the likely surface deposition, mainly of KCl, which is readily water soluble. The RF of sulphur (S) shows the opposite behaviour, and the difference between the RF is increasing when progressing through the subsequent leaching steps. A possible explanation can be sought in the sonochemistry, meaning that the presence of ultrasound often acts as an enabler for many chemical reactions. For instance, the release of gaseous sulphur, e.g., as SO₂ or H₂S could take place, but this cannot be confirmed here, as the gas composition was not measured during these experiments. What was observed is a lower pH of the leachate in the ultrasound-assisted experiment in comparison to the reference experiment (**Figure 32**). The elemental ICP analysis of the ash after the last leaching step did not reveal large differences between the experiment with ultrasound and the reference experiment, as shown in **Figure 33** for the selected elements.

During the 60-minutes experiment with ultrasound a temperature rise of the leachate was observed, which was caused by the dissipation of the ultrasound energy. Due to the lack of active cooling in the ultrasonic bath it was not possible to maintain a constant leaching temperature (here: 25°C). Therefore, the results are considered biased, as they combine two effects, namely the presence of ultrasound and a temperature rise, and it is not possible to distinguish between them. For this reason, a further analysis of these results is omitted here.

In general, regarding the ultrasound-assisted leaching experiments it can be concluded that there is a large positive effect mainly on the release of the compounds deposited on the surface of the leached substrate, and possibly also some sonochemistry effects are also present, but the obtained dataset does not allow to assess them quantitatively nor qualitatively. Due to the technical limitations, it was not possible to maintain a constant temperature during the experiments with duration longer than 5 minutes. Both for the reason of unclear effects on the leaching process and technical limitations it was decided not to continue the ultrasound-assisted experiments during this stage of the project, but a new experiment will be taken into consideration at a later stage (WP8, *Technology validation: SOEC and gasification residues recovery, T8.2, Leaching conditions validation*).

Figure 30. A comparison of the effect of ultrasound on the recovered fraction of selected elements (experiment no. 6) vs the reference experiment (no. 1). Recovered fractions obtained after step 1

Figure 31. A comparison of the effect of ultrasound on the recovered fraction of selected elements (experiment no. 6) vs the reference experiment (no. 1). Recovered fractions obtained after 5 steps (cumulative).

Figure 32. A comparison of the effect of ultrasound on pH (experiment no. 6) vs the reference experiment (no. 1).

Figure 33. A comparison of the effect of ultrasound on concentration of elements in the ash before and after leaching process.

5.4.3 Effect of drying between the steps

As described in the previous sections of this chapter, each leaching experiment consisted of a number of leaching steps, and the leached substrate (char, ash) was dried between the subsequent steps. Different results (see Section 5.2) point out that this can be an important part of an effective recovery process, but in an industrial environment such an intermediate and repeated drying step can be logistically complicated and, moreover, energy consuming. Therefore, an experiment was planned to directly compare the leaching performance with and without intermediate drying.

Figure 34 presents a comparison of the effect of ultrasound on the recovered fraction of selected elements in a reference experiment (experiment no. 24, with drying) and experiment no. 25 (no drying before step 2). In this figure the recovered fractions apply to the second step only, they are not the cumulative of step 1 and 2. The effect of the inter-step drying is clearly visible for all selected elements. For potassium (K) the relative RF increase due to drying is ca. 15%, for S and P around 100%, for Mg 73%. The highest gain is observed for Zn, ca. 600%, while also Pb is detected in the leachate when drying is applied. Hence it can be concluded that the effect of drying is unambiguous.

Figure 34. A comparison of the effect of inter-step drying on the recovered fraction. Recovered fractions of selected elements from the second steps of experiment no. 24 (with drying, reference experiment) and experiment no. 25 (no drying before step 2). Recovered fractions apply to the second step only.

The exact mechanism behind the inter-step drying is not yet fully investigated. Different physical and chemical mechanisms can play a role, among them the phase changes of different species (e.g. from KCl dissolved as ions to a solid compound), hydrate forming and dehydration, chemical reactions with steam in the micropores, or structural changes by steam explosions, again on a micro scale. Surely it is one of the more interesting phenomena observed during this research work, together with the stepwise increase of the leaching performance, and therefore will be investigated in more depth during the further implementation of the project (WP8, *Technology validation: SOEC and gasification residues recovery*, T8.2, *Leaching conditions validation*).

6 Leaching experiments - Batch experiments in a pressurized reactor

6.1 Introduction

In the previous section the results of the batch experiments carried out in an open system were described. These experiments provided a significant insight into the correlation between the leaching effectiveness and the applied leaching process parameters. However, one of the limitations of that process was the lack of ability to control the gaseous atmosphere and to measure the gases which were evolving during the leaching. The fact that some gas release took place was observed during the *in vitro* batch experiments and also predicted by the initial FactSage simulations (see Section 8). This was the reason to attempt to apply a closed system for the leaching experiments.

6.2 Methodology

A commercial pressurized laboratory reactor (Parr) with the total volume of 1000 mL was selected as the reaction vessel. The reactor was entirely made of stainless steel (AISI 316). The maximum operating pressure was 180 bar (the setting of the pressure relief valve) at the temperature of 200°C. On the top cover different process connections were available, to install relevant process equipment and sensors. For the leaching experiments the reactor was equipped with a pressure gauge, a temperature sensor (PT 100) and two needle valves allowing the supply and removal of liquids and/or gases. In order to protect the inner surface of the reactor from the interaction with the reactants, a beaker-shaped PTFE insert was installed. The entire reactor was placed on an integrated heat plate and magnetic stirrer, which allowed the controlled heating and stirring of the reactor contents. The temperature sensor inside the reactor was connected to the temperature controller of the heat plate, allowing to directly control the temperature inside the reactor.

The gas atmosphere in the reactor was created by supplying compressed air and nitrogen (5.0 grade), from gas cylinders. To monitor the changes in the gas composition during the experiment two different devices were used:

- a portable gas analyser BIOGAS 5000, capable of measuring CO, CO₂, CH₄, O₂ and H₂S;
- a gas chromatograph (SRI 8610) with a ShinCarbon ST 80-100 column and a TCD detector, capable of measuring H₂, N₂/O₂, CO, CO₂, CH₄. In this configuration no N₂/O₂ separation could be achieved, therefore the combined peak was considered as an “air” peak.

A picture of the reactor on the heat plate and the gas analyser is shown in Figure 35.

Figure 35. A picture of the pressurized laboratory reactor setup. [Source: RIC]

The following range of operational parameters was used during the leaching experiments:

- Leaching media: distilled water;
- Char: MMX;
- Process temperatures: 60, 120 and 160°C;
- Process pressures: 1, 10 and 20 bar;
- Process atmospheres: air, nitrogen (N₂);
- Liquid to solid ratio (w/w): 10:1;
- Leaching durations: 60 and 120 minutes;
- Stirring: 600 rpm.

A batch of char was weighted on a laboratory scale and put into the reactor. Then the reactor cover was closed and the reactor volume was flushed with the desired gas for approximately 10 minutes. Once completed, the reactor was filled with a predetermined mass of the leaching medium, to achieve the desired liquid to solid (L/S) ratio. Finally, the reactor contents were brought to the desired initial pressure by filling the volume with the appropriate gas. Then the stirring and heating was started and the actual experiment commenced.

During the experiment the composition of the gas was periodically measured by releasing the gas using one of the needle valves to flush the gas path of the gas analyser and the sampling loop of the gas chromatograph (GC). The flow of the sample was monitored using a rotameter and a pressure gauge. The gas analyser readings were available instantaneously, while one GC run took 15 minutes.

After the experiment the leachate was decanted and analysed using the cuvette tests for the selected elements.

6.3 Results

6.3.1 Gas atmosphere comparison

The effect of creating a specific (inert or oxidating) atmosphere on the recovered fraction (RF) and the gaseous products generated during the leaching process was investigated.

The operational parameters used for the atmosphere comparison experiments were:

- Leaching medium: distilled water;
- Maximum process temperature: 160°C;
- Starting pressure: 10 bar;
- Process atmosphere: air, nitrogen;
- Leaching duration: 120 minutes.

The results are presented in Figure 36. The gaseous atmosphere exposes a minor impact on the RF of elements in a single step experiment: the results for K and Mg were better for the air atmosphere (a relative increase of 13.3% for K), while in the nitrogen atmosphere better results were obtained for S, P and Pb (a relative decrease of 11.6% for S and 27.0% for P). Interestingly, the changes observed for K, S, P and Mg are corresponding to these observed during the ultrasound-assisted experiments (see Section 5.4.2, **Figure 30** and Figure 31), although there the difference for K and S was more pronounced there. The measurements of the outlet gas from the reactor indicate a more extensive formation of the gaseous products in the presence of oxygen. In the atmosphere containing oxygen, 779 ppm of CO and 1.6% of CO₂ were measured at a maximum, while in the anaerobic atmosphere, the measured amount of CO was only 59 ppm, and CO₂ was 0.1%, by volume. When the formation of gases was observed for the first time during the *in vitro* batch experiments it was expected that the gas would be CO₂. This expectation was based on the possible presence of carbonates in the char. The release of CO₂ was, however, not expected to depend on the gaseous atmosphere, although the gaseous atmosphere was expected to have a certain influence on the leaching process. The results of the FactSage simulations (see Section 8) indicated also the possibility of methane (CH₄) release, with methane being the main gas released during the leaching, but this was not confirmed during any of the experiments conducted in the pressurised reactor. In addition, it has to be stressed that the gas composition measurements done using BIOGAS 5000 were not confirmed by the GC measurements. The GC

measurements did not yield any meaningful results, no identifiable gas peaks were detected other than the “air” peak.

Figure 36. A comparison of the effect of the applied gaseous atmosphere on the recovered fraction (left) and the results of the gas composition measurements (right) in the pressurised reactor. Applied process conditions: MMX char, $T=160^{\circ}\text{C}$, $p_0=10\text{ bar}$, $t=120\text{min}$, 1 step).

6.3.2 Leaching systems comparison: pressure reactor vs open system

Leaching in the pressure reactor (PR) was compared to the open *in vitro* batch system (B), and the effects of elevated temperature and an increased pressure were observed. As mentioned earlier, the vessel size and the stirring intensity influence the RF. Therefore, an experiment was carried out at the same temperature and for the same duration as in the previously done *in-vitro* (beaker) experiment. The results are shown in Figure 37.

When considering only a single step experiment, the results obtained in the PR generally show progressing increase in RFs with the temperature, the highest for K, except an anomaly at 120°C . Also S and P show a positive trend, although the differences are less pronounced. Interestingly, the RF of Pb is decreasing with the temperature and this is also observed during the experiments with the Advanced Solvent Extraction described in Section 7). When comparing to a complete *in vitro* water leaching sequence (five steps), the total RF obtained in the beaker is higher than in the PR for all selected elements. This confirms earlier observations made in Section 5 that the number of leaching steps (and probably not just the step, but the inter-step drying of the char) has a bigger effect on the RF than the leaching time or temperature. For some elements, here in particular the phosphorus (P) the second step (or the first inter-step drying) acts as an enabler for the release of these elements.

During the experiments with the PR, due to the thermal inertia of the reactor it was not possible to carry out experiments shorter than 60 minutes, and for temperatures above 100°C shorter than 120 minutes. Also, after the experiment the reactor had to be cooled down to a temperature below 100°C , before it could be opened and the contents removed. Therefore, the actual exposure to the elevated temperature was longer than the nominal duration, causing a certain bias in the comparison. Nonetheless the trends can be compared and the results used for the further analysis and the conceptual design of the leaching process.

Figure 37. A comparison of the effect of the leaching methods on the RF: *in-vitro* batch/beaker experiments (BiV) after the 1st step and the cumulative RF after the 5th step; pressure reactor (PR) operating at different temperatures and initial pressures, single step. Leached substrate: MMX char.

6.3.3 Multi-step experiment

To extend the temperature range applied during the leaching experiments also including the effect of the leaching step and the inter-step drying an experiment consisting of a sequence of three leaching steps was done.

The operational parameters used for the three-step experiment were:

- Step 1:
 - Maximum process temperature: 120°C;
 - Starting pressure: atmospheric pressure;
 - Process atmosphere: air.
- Step 2:
 - Maximum process temperature: 120°C;
 - Maximum pressure: 10 bar;
 - Process atmosphere: nitrogen.
- Step 3:
 - Maximum process temperature: 160°C;
 - Maximum pressure: 20 bar;
 - Process atmosphere: nitrogen;
- All steps:
 - Char type: MMX;
 - Leaching medium: distilled water;
 - Liquid to solid ratio (w/w): 10:1;
 - Nominal leaching duration: 120 minutes;
 - Stirring: 600 rpm.

Figure 38. A comparison of the step-by-step RF cumulation during the 3-step experiment in the pressurized reactor.

This experiment was also meant to explore different process limits and their effect on the leaching process, and to gain more insight into which parameters do have or do not have any influence on the release of the elements into the leachate.

Figure 38 shows the cumulative RFs of the selected elements achieved during the 3-step experiment. The data of Step 1 corresponds to the data shown in **Figure 37** labelled “PR_120°C_120min”. Analysing the results per element the following observations can be made:

- K: compared to the open system leaching performed at 60°C the total RF after three steps is minimally lower, 67.3% vs 71.6%. The contributions of Step 2 and Step 3 are slightly higher than in the case of the open system (respectively 22.5% and 14.9% vs 19.4% and 9.5%), but the difference in Step 1 determines the difference for the sum of the three steps;
- S: comparing again to the open system, the total RF after three steps is higher: 36.4% vs 30.6%. All individual steps yield a higher RF, contributing to the total difference 6.4%-points;
- P: as in the case of S, the total RF achieved in the PR is higher than in the open system, 15.1% vs 13.2%. However, the contribution of the individual steps is different: in the PR steps 1 and 2 contribute an approximately equal share, with Step 1 being higher than Step 2, while in the open system (and at lower temperature, just as a reminder) the contribution of Step 2 is nearly double of that in Step 1. This is the “activation effect” of the first step or in fact of the first inter-step drying, as discussed earlier. Furthermore, the RF increase in Step 3 in the PR is only 1.1%-point vs 3.5%-point in the open system;
- Mg and Pb: in both cases the cumulative RFs are lower than in the open system, namely 1.22 and 0.36 vs 2.96% and 0.82%, respectively. In all three steps the RF of Mg in the PR is lower, while Pb is not detected at all in steps 1 and 3, while it is detected in all steps in the open system;
- Zn: this element is not detected in none of the steps during the leaching in the open system, while it is consequently present in the leachate from the PR, steps 1 – 3, in approximately equal shares. Its recovery can be attributed to the higher leaching temperature than in the case of the open system. The influence of the gaseous atmosphere is unclear and would require further investigation.

In general, it can be concluded that the overall performance of the PR in terms of the RFs of individual elements is worse than of the open system. The RFs of P and S are slightly higher, but that comes at the cost of significantly higher temperatures and a more complex process equipment. In addition, the presence of Zn is not desirable, as it is preferred only to have potential nutrients or elements which are neutral from the environment and health point of view recovered in the water leaching steps, while (heavy metals) would be separated afterwards.

7 Leaching experiments - Batch experiments using Accelerated Solvent Extraction (ASE)

7.1 Introduction

In the previous section the results of the experiments with a pressure reactor system applied to the leaching experiments were described. That system allowed to perform leaching experiments at significantly higher temperatures than the open system, and allowed also to do a preliminary investigation of the effect of the different gaseous atmospheres above the leachate, as well as monitor the evolution of the gas composition. Although the experiments with the pressure reactor provided new valuable information, it was relatively difficult to achieve repeatability, especially regarding the pressure, temperature and leaching duration, which are in fact the key process parameters. In order to address this shortcoming, but still obtain more insight into the effect of leaching at elevated pressures and temperatures a series of experiments was performed using an Accelerated Solvent Extraction system (ASE).

7.2 Methodology

Accelerated Solvent Extraction device (Dionex ASE 350) is an automatic system for extracting organic and inorganic substances from variety of solid or semi-solid samples with varying pH. The device can operate at temperatures up to 200°C and pressures up to 1700 psi (117.2 bar). Extraction is carried out in 100 mL stainless steel vials, and the extracts are filtered using Whatman ME25/21 ST membrane 0.45µm filters. A picture of the device is shown in Figure 39.

Figure 39. A picture of Dionex ASE 350 Advanced Solvent Extraction system at RIC. [Source: RIC]

Figure 40. A photo of 100 mL stainless steel cell (on the right) and the bottles with leachates collected during the experiments. [Source: RIC]

Leaching experiments using the ASE were conducted to investigate the effects of high temperatures and high pressures on the leaching of the individual elements, as well as to investigate the effect of the leaching ratio (L/S). The experiments were carried out with the following operating parameters:

- Char: MMX;
- Leaching medium: distilled water;
- Process temperature: 25, 60 and 200°C;
- Process pressure: 110 bar;
- Liquid to solid ratio (w/w): 5:1, 10:1, 20:1;
- Leaching durations: 5 minutes;
- Additional information: the multi-step experiments were conducted without inter-step drying.

Table 7 shows the combinations of parameters that were used. The cell (vial) must always be full of liquid in order to create high pressure. The ASE device can only measure the amount of solvent injected, and there is no possibility to set the volume to be dosed. Therefore, to achieve the desired leaching ratio, it was necessary to perform a series of pretests to determine the optimal weight of the char samples for the specified values of the leaching ratio.

During the experiments with different leaching ratios a problem with cell clogging was encountered at a leaching ratio lower than 10:1. This was probably due to the inability to stir the char during experiments in the ASE. After conducting several trials, the leaching ratio 5:1 experiment using ASE was abandoned.

Table 7. Batch experiments matrix in the ASE.

Leaching ratio Leaching temperature	5:1	10:1	20:1
25°C	X	X	X
60°C		X	
200°C		X	

After the experiment the collected leachates were analysed using the cuvette tests to measure the concentrations of the selected elements: K, S, P, Mg and Pb. Similar to other experiments, the measured concentrations were multiplied by the leachate volumes to obtain the total mass of the elements separated (extracted) from the char. Then the recovered fraction (RF) was calculated by dividing the mass of the extracted element by its initial amount in the substrate, being the product of the mass of the char input and the concentration of the respective element in the char. Here the results of the elemental char analysis by ETL were used as reference.

7.3 Results

7.3.1 Leaching temperature comparison

The results of the influence of leaching temperature under pressurized leaching conditions on the separation efficiency of selected elements in 5-step leaching sequences are presented below, with Figure 41 showing the cumulative recovery fractions of the analysed elements after five steps, while Figure 43 shows the RF cumulated per step, so the contribution of each step to the total RF can be visualized. The positive effect of the increasing leaching temperature on the RF of K and S is clearly visible, yielding respectively a 2.8x and 2.3x increase at 200°C when comparing to the RF achieved at 25°C. There is no noticeable effect on the RFs of P and Mg; both values drop slightly when moving from 25°C to 60°C and then remain nearly constant at 200°C. The RF of Pb shows a decreasing trend, moving from 1.29% at 25°C to 0% at 200°C. The same behaviour was independently observed during the pressure reactor (PR) experiments (see Section 6.3.2).

Further comparison of the influence of the leaching temperature on the RF of specific elements per leaching step reveals four different trends, see Figure 43:

1. The RF of K exhibits a logarithmic relationship with the leaching temperature, shown in Figure 41 and the effect of each subsequent leaching step is enhanced the higher the temperature (the trendlines in **Figure 42** are diverging). It is also clear that the further increase of the temperature will likely cause the RF to asymptotically approach to a value of about 80% for the 5th step, at least if no other physical or chemical phenomena will occur.
2. The RF of S reveals a stepwise increase in RF at 200°C, while the RFs achieved at 25°C and 60°C are very similar. This indicates the enabling of a sulphur release mechanism at temperatures between 60 and 200°C. As in the case of K, Step 1 contributes the most to the RF, and then both add approximately one-third more recovery in the subsequent four steps (34 and 30% extra relative to Step 1 for K and S, respectively).
3. The RFs of P and Mg show a trend partly opposite to S and K. While the first step yields the highest RF at 200°C, in particular for P, where the RF of step 1 at 200°C is nearly double the value achieved at 25 and 60°C, in the subsequent steps the cumulative RF at 200°C flattens out (for P already in Step 3, for Mg in Step 5) causing the final value in Step 5 to be lower than the RF at 25°C and similar to the RF at 60°C. Such behaviour suggests a phase change or the rearrangement of the P- and Mg-containing compound(s) towards the molecules with lower solubility in water at 200°C. For P this could possibly be attributed to the transition from white P to red-P, which takes place exactly around 200°C, with red-P being poorly soluble in water (see Section 3.3.5).
4. The RF of Pb decreases with increasing temperature, and at 200°C no Pb is found in the leachates, not even after five steps. A similar observation was already made during the experiments with the pressure reactor (see Section 6.3.3). At the moment of writing of this document no explanation can yet be given for such results, but it is an interesting phenomenon for further investigation as it can be an asset when planning the entire chain of char/ash leaching with the separation of specific elements, with heavy metals like Pb being one of the key categories of interest.

Figure 41. Leaching temperature comparison with ASE (MMX, 5 min, 5 step experiments).

Figure 42. Recovered fraction (RF) of potassium (K) plotted versus leaching temperature for the leaching steps 1 - 5.

Figure 43. Graphs of cumulated recovery fractions per leaching step for K, S, P, Mg and Pb.

7.3.2 Leaching ratio comparison

A series of experiments was performed to assess the effect of the leaching ratio in ASE, and compare it to the results obtained in the BiV leaching. Due to the fact that the actual amount of the dosed liquid cannot be predefined in the used ASE system, the leaching ratio had to be obtained using a targeted trial and error method, therefore the two experiments at a nominal L/S of 20:1 in the end resulted in the actual L/S of respectively 18.6:1 and 20.5:1. The ASE results are shown in **Figure 44**, while the BiV results are shown in **Figure 45**. Due to the blockage of the system, the experiment at the L/S of 5:1 using ASE had to be abandoned – this was due to a too low “flowability” of the char suspension, not because of the equipment failure.

Both experiments showed that there is hardly any added value of the leaching ratio higher than 10:1. In the ASE experiment only lead showed a higher RF at the L/S of 20.5:1, but the much lower value at 18.6:1 did not confirm this trend. The remaining elements, K, S, P and Mg show lower or similar RFs at L/S of 20 than at the L/S of 10:1.

A similar trend can be observed for the BiV experiments, although a minute improvement was noted for K, and almost the doubling of the RFs of P and Mg. There is, however, an additional difference that can be observed in the figures below, namely that the RFs of especially potassium are higher at all L/S ratios in the BiV experiments than in ASE experiments. The most straightforward conclusion to explain this fact is the stirring of the reactor contents. The importance of stirring was already indicated in Section 5.4.1, and it is confirmed here. As the residence times are short (5 minutes) the water-soluble potassium which is likely deposited on or close to the surface of the char particles benefits from mechanical agitation to enter the solution in a higher amount. The high pressure in the ASE system, which could be expected to force the leaching agent deep into the pores of the char did not provide the same effect as mechanical stirring, or ultrasound as mentioned in Section 5.4.2.

Figure 44. Leaching ratio comparison using ASE and the MMX char. All experiments performed at a temperature of 25°C with the leaching duration of 5 minutes.

Figure 45. Leaching ratio comparison using BiV and the MMX char.

7.3.3 Leaching performance comparison: ASE vs open system vs pressure reactor

Finally, the results obtained with the ASE were compared to the results obtained using other leaching processes, namely to the open system and the pressure reactor. The goal of comparing these three processes is to obtain an additional insight into the influence of different process parameters and conditions on the leaching efficiency expressed as the recovered fraction (RF) of the selected elements.

The operational parameters used in the experiment described below were:

- Char: MMX;
- Raw char ICP analysis dataset: ETL;
- Step time: 5 min
- Temp.: 25°C

Figure 46 presents a comparison between the RFs obtained in the experiments with the ASE and in the open system after five steps. The differences between these two experimental conditions are:

- stirring: ASE – no; OS – yes;
- pressure: ASE – 110 bar; OS – atmospheric;
- liquid volume: ASE – 100 ml; OS – 1 L
- .

From this figure it is clear that the leaching at ambient temperature in the open system achieves higher or similar RFs for all analysed elements. For the elements K, S and P the differences are large (47% lower RF for S, and even more for P and K). It can be concluded that just the application of high pressure does not compensate for the lack of stirring during the leaching at low temperature.

Figure 46. Leaching methods comparison: Beaker vs ASE (MMX, 25°C, 5 min, 5 step experiments).

This picture changes at higher leaching temperatures, as already discussed in the Section 7.3.1 based on the series of 3 ASE experiments. Figure 47 presents a comparison between different leaching temperatures and different leaching processes: the open system (beaker, B), pressure reactor (PR) and ASE. The presented RFs apply to a single-step leaching process (Step 1). These results again confirm the positive effect on the leaching of especially K, S and P. In addition to the observations already described in Section 7.3.1 it can be concluded that the best first step performance in terms of the highest RF is achieved in the PR at 160°C for K and P, followed by ASE. Sulphur (S) shows the second-highest RF, preceded by ASE. At lower temperatures, below 100°C, i.e. the boiling point of water at atmospheric pressure leaching in the open system yields higher or similar RF values than ASE.

Figure 47. A comparison of recovered fractions (RF) achieved in a single step (Step 1) vs the applied leaching temperature and the leaching process: open system (beaker, BiV), ASE and pressure reactor (PR). Experiment (E) numbers indicated between brackets.

Leaching parameters comparison (Beaker vs Pressure Reactor vs ASE)

Figure 48. A comparison of recovered fractions (RF) achieved in a single step (Step 1) vs the applied leaching temperature and the leaching process: open system (beaker, BiV), ASE and pressure reactor (PR). Experiment (E) numbers indicated between brackets.

Figure 49. A comparison of recovered fractions (RF) achieved in a single step (Step 1) at 60°C vs the applied leaching process: open system (beaker, BiV), ASE and pressure reactor (PR). Experiment (E) numbers indicated between brackets.

8 FactSage simulations

8.1 Introduction

In the previous sections the results of the leaching experiments were presented and discussed. These experiments yielded many interesting and relevant observations related to the leaching process and the influence of the leaching conditions on the mobilisation of the elements present in the solid substrate into the leachate. In order to gain better understanding of the underlying phenomena and the ability to predict the influence of the leaching parameters on the leaching efficiency the experimental work was supported by the chemical equilibrium simulations. The aim of the simulations was to evaluate the influence of the process conditions and, at the later stage, to create a tool for the prediction of the effect of the leaching conditions on a specific substrate (char or ash).

The chemical equilibrium simulations were performed using FactSage™ software, version 8.3. FactSage™ is a simulation package to perform calculations based on the Gibbs' free energy minimisation. It includes extensive databases with the chemical properties of pure substances, compounds and solutions, allowing to calculate the equilibrium composition at different temperatures and pressures, and to predict the effect of changing any of these parameters as well as the effect of adding, for example a new reactant or changing the leaching medium. The FactSage™ package consists of different modules, and the “home screen” of the software is shown in **Figure 50**. For the work presented in this section the “Equilib” module was mostly used.

Figure 50. FactSage™ version 8.3 welcome screen.

FactSage simulations have several advantages for its use in the research work described in this report. The simulations do not require very powerful hardware but nonetheless are fast. The software is also relatively easy to use, at least in its basic functionality. Process boundaries can be easily explored computationally, also at process conditions that would be difficult to achieve in the laboratory or would require special equipment. The “Equilib” simulation should be seen as a reactor vessel that is filled with the chemical species specified in the input data – these can include all phases (solid, liquid, gaseous); also, the elements can be included in the input data (e.g. elemental hydrogen, H, and elemental oxygen, O, without specifying if it should be H₂, O₂ or maybe H₂O or H₂O₂). Further, the specification of the thermodynamic variables should be provided, typically being the pressure and the temperature,

but also the final volume, volume change, enthalpy change (e.g. $\Delta H=0$ for an isenthalpic process, or $\Delta S=0$ for an isentropic process) could be specified as well. With these input data and based on the selected compound databases the software will calculate the equilibrium composition. Taking the example of the H and O input: if 1 gram of each element is specified as the input, with 25°C and 1 bar temperature and pressure, respectively, the output will yield 1.1303 gram of the ideal gas mixture consisting of 96.8%-mol of H₂ and 3.2%-mol of water vapour, as well as 0.86974 gram of the aqueous phase being liquid H₂O. Also, minor amounts of the OH⁻ and H⁺ ions are returned, as well as traces of dissolved hydrogen.

Naturally, as every model or calculation tool, FactSage™ or more generally speaking the equilibrium-based approach has its limitations. From the point of view of the research presented in this work, two limitations are of the main importance:

- the first, which is inherent to the chemical equilibrium approach is the neglect of the reaction mechanisms and the kinetic effects. The model will (in most cases) generate an output, which, in simplification will reflect the state of the input mixture at an infinite residence time. No diffusion or rate effects will be taken into account;
- the second, which in fact applies to every model or calculation is the dependency of the quality and usefulness of its results on the accuracy of the provided input data.

Both limitations will be taken into account and discussed in the sections below, where appropriate. Nonetheless, chemical equilibrium modelling is a very powerful tool, especially in complex systems where it would be very difficult or even impossible to define each relevant reaction scheme.

The following sections describe the results of the first set of FactSage™ simulations performed in parallel to the leaching experiments.

8.2 Raw ash composition simulations

As mentioned in the introduction to this section (8.1) the results of the calculations strongly depend on the provided input data. In the case of the leaching process simulations the composition of the input material will be of key importance. Here, the “composition” does not only refer to the elemental composition as described in the Section 3.2 and in Appendix I. Already in the earlier research work it was shown, that this approach will lead to erroneous results [28]. Furthermore, it was also mentioned that the XRD analysis did not yield any useful results that could help in the identification of the chemical compounds present in the biomass char, but in case of the ash already some crystalline structures could be identified, as shown in **Figure 2** on page 9. Also, the NMR approach was unsuccessful [6]. Therefore, before the actual leaching simulations, the simulations to identify the compounds constituting the char were performed. The initial simulations, however, were done using the MA ash, due to the fact, that the influence of the carbon matrix was lower (lower amount of carbon present in the ash than in the char), and in addition the abovementioned XRD data was available, which would provide additional validation data.

The input of the simulations consisted of the elemental composition data from the CHNSO, ICP (by PPNT lab) and XRF (chlorine) analyses of MMX ash. The share of individual compounds per 100 g of char is given **Table 8**. As can be seen, the values do not sum up to 100. However, for the simulations the values were not normalized, but used “as is”.

Table 8. The elemental composition of MMX char, combined from different analytical methods. Values in g / 100 g and sorted in descending order.

C	O	Si	Al	K	Cl	Ca	H	P	Mg	As	Fe
56.590	8.900	7.2360	6.2113	4.1077	2.860	2.5157	0.800	0.7976	0.5080	0.3870	0.2608
Ti	Na	Zn	S	Li	Sr	Mn	Zr	Ba	B	Pb	Sum
0.2432	0.2371	0.2172	0.2109	0.0918	0.0547	0.0410	0.0305	0.0266	0.0222	0.0220	92.371

Furthermore, three temperature levels (25°C, 550°C and 850°C) and a single pressure setting (1 bar(a), i.e. atmospheric pressure) were chosen. These temperatures refer to the equilibration of the elements at ambient conditions, exposure to the temperature at which the char is generated, and the

temperature in the biomass gasifier. In these simulations no gaseous atmosphere was applied, which means that all the elements should be included in the output solid mass. This assumption was correct, since the elemental analysis referred to the solid material and the mass balance must be respected. In order to complete the input, the following compound databases were selected:

- FactPS – FACT pure substances database (2023), contains data for 5038 compounds (pure substances) comprising 7167 phases;
- FTsalt - FACT salt compounds and solutions (2023) - contains data for pure salts and salt solutions formed among various combinations of the 27 main cations Li, Na, K, Rb, Cs, Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba, Mn, Al, Fe(II), Fe(III), Co, Ni, Zn, Pb, La, Ce, Th, U(III), U(IV), Pu(III), Pu(IV), Cr(II), Cr(III), Mo(V) and 10 main anions F, Cl, Br, I, NO₂, NO₃, ClO₄, OH, CO₃, SO₄;
- FTmisc – FACT miscellaneous compounds and solutions (2023) – databases for sulphides, alloys, etc.

With the input described above, three simulation runs were performed. Their results are presented in **Table 9**. The results consisted of a list of chemical compounds and their masses, with the total set having the minimum Gibbs free energy at the specified temperature. The small differences between the total input mass and the total output mass result from the fact, that the simulation uses iterative calculations with a specified mass balance convergence threshold. Also, the names of the chemical species or their phases are provided, where available.

For all simulated temperatures the main constituent of the ash is carbon, here as graphite, which is an amorphous carbon and therefore can be used as an approximation of the carbon present in the ash, which is also amorphous, as also confirmed by the XRD analysis. Some of the carbon, together with Si formed silicon carbide (SiC), and its amount increased at 850°C compared to both lower temperatures. Silicon is further bound in silicates and aluminosilicates of K, Na, Ca and Mg. Potassium aluminosilicates transform into smaller molecules with increasing temperature. The amount of KCl, being the only Cl-containing compound predicted to be formed at 25°C and 550°C decreases at the highest temperature, due to the transfer of a part of Cl to CaCl₂(H₂O)₆ (Antarctite). Approximately one-third of the phosphorus (P) input is predicted to occur in the ash as red phosphorus at 25 and 550°C, but then changing structure to white phosphorus at 850°C. This is an important change, because as mentioned in Section 3.3, white P is water-soluble, while red P is not. The remaining P is predicted to be bound by the metals as phosphides (FeP₂, Zn₃P₂, MnP₃) – their amounts remain relatively stable at all three temperature levels. Multiple metals are present as hydrides (AlH₃, LiAlH₄, MgH₂, TiH₂, ZrH₂ and BaH₂). Arsenic (As) and lead (Pb) are present in their metallic form, irrespectively of the temperature. This suggests poor water leachability of lead, and a better suitability of acidic leaching agents, capable of dissolving the metal.

The qualitative comparison of the simulation results to the XRD spectrum of MA ash shown in **Figure 2** confirms the presence of KCl and carbon. In the ash spectrum also three phosphates were identified, while the simulation did not predict any phosphates, but rather phosphides. Potential similarities can be sought between MnP₃ (simulation) and Mn_{0.42}B_{0.58}PO₄ (XRD), as well as FeP₂ (simulation) and Ca_{28.8}Fe_{3.2}(PO₄)₂₁O₅ (XRD). No compound containing Zn and P was identified on the XRD, even though the amount of Zn present in the ash was higher than of Mn and B, and similar to the amount of Fe. Interestingly, in the XRD spectrum Al₂O₃ was identified, with was not present among the results of the simulation at 850°C, but was present in the results of 25°C and, more importantly 550°C, as hydrate.

Considering the results presented and discussed above, and taking into account that the MA ash actually was exposed to temperatures around 850°C, the results of the simulation at 850°C were selected as the input for the water leaching simulations, which results are presented in the next section. Obviously, the results of the simulations to predict the ash composition are not yet satisfactory, but they need to be considered as preliminary results. One of the common methods used in chemical equilibrium modelling is the use of the “quasi-equilibrium” conditions, to reflect the fact that in the actual process at actual process conditions the equilibrium is not reached. This can be done by running a simulation at, for example, a lower temperature (the “quasi-equilibrium temperature”), with the aim to obtain the results achieved in the validation experiment. If, taking the results discussed above, the presence of Al₂O₃ would be consistently confirmed in chemical analyses, then it could be an option to use the results of the simulation at 550°C as the ash composition, even though the actual process temperature was 850°C. Naturally, this is just an example, as this will also affect other compounds. The quasi-equilibrium approach is planned to be implemented in the next part of the simulation work.

Another method to cope with the discrepancies between the modelling results and the experimental validation is the sensitivity analysis. As shown in **Table 8**, the sum of the masses of individual elements does not equal 100 g, meaning that approximately 8 grams was not identified or measured. As each measurement method will have a certain measurement error it is important to know if a specific value has a large influence on the relevant result or not. **Table 10** presents the results of a simple sensitivity assessment analysis the influence of the amount of the element O (oxygen) in the elemental composition. Three simulations were run, with different initial amounts of O, namely 8.9 g (a base case value, as in the simulations described above), 11.9 g and 17.9 g, as an extreme value giving a large excess oxygen. The runs were performed at a single temperature of 850°C. One of the hypotheses was that a higher availability of oxygen will yield the presence of metal oxides, e.g., PbO, and also the formation of phosphates (PO_4) instead of phosphides.

The results of the simulations did not confirm these hypotheses. Starting from the trace elements, no metal oxides were formed, and both Pb and As remained in their metallic form, even with high oxygen availability. Also, the phosphorus compounds remained unaffected. Only at the highest input amount some Al_2O_3 was formed. Most of the additional oxygen was consumed by the potassium aluminosilicate, which transformed from KAlSiO_4 to KAlSi_2O_6 . Also, the mass of hydrated CaCl_2 increased from ca. 2.8 g to ca. 8.8 g, a nearly threefold increase. There was also some migration of Mg, from MgH_2 to a complex magnesium aluminosilicate hydroxide, but again only at the highest oxygen input amount. These results show that the change in the oxygen input amount did not cause the expected changes in the calculated ash compositions, and also did not bring the simulation results closer to the available validation data. In this context it can be concluded that the amount of oxygen in the input is not a sensitive parameter.

These results are a part of the first set of simulations, which allowed to set out the path for further work in the project. This work will involve a study of the process conditions that are required to or that facilitate the formation of specific compounds, here for example phosphates. On the other hand, additional validation data will be obtained, mainly related to the analysis of the compounds present in the solid substrate. As the analysis of the raw char has turned out to be complicated in the case of XRD, two parallel paths are considered: focus on the ash, and simultaneously work on the selective low-temperature oxidation of the carbon in the char, such that the inorganic part is minimally affected but the bulk carbon is removed.

Table 9. The results of FactSage simulations of the MA ash composition. The values are in grams per 100 nominal grams of the model char.

Final temperature: 25°C			Final temperature: 550°C			Final temperature: 850°C		
Chemical formula	Name	Mass	Chemical formula	Name	Mass	Chemical formula	Name	Mass
C(s)	Graphite	54.82	C(s)	Graphite	54.840	C(s)	Graphite	54.09
KAl3Si3O10(OH)2(s)	Muscovite	8.897	KCl(s)	Sylvite_rocksalt	6.014	SiC(s2)	Solid_Beta	8.331
KCl(s)	Sylvite_rocksalt	6.014	SiC(s2)	Solid_Beta	5.858	(CaO)4(Al2O3)(H2O)1	solid	6.347
SiC(s2)	Solid_Beta	5.9	KAlSi2O6(s)	Leucite(RHF)-A	4.875	KAlSiO4(s2)	Kaliophilite-or	6.256
AlH3(s)	Solid_(hexagona	3.623	H4SiO4(s)	solid	4.231	KCl(s)	Sylvite_rocksalt	4.731
Na2Ca3Si6O16(s)	solid	3.046	Al2O3(H2O)(s2)	Boehmite	3.890	AlH3(s)	Solid_(hexagonal)	2.936
Mg5Al2Si3O10(OH)8(s)	clinochlorite	2.323	AlH3(s)	Solid_(hexagonal)	3.334	CaMg2Al16O27(s)	solid	2.776
CaH2(s)	solid	1.714	CaH2(s)	solid	2.365	CaCl2(H2O)6(s)	Antarcticite	1.886
H2O(s)	Ice	1.599	Mg5Al2Si3O10(OH)8(s)	clinochlorite	2.323	NaAlSiO4(s)	Nepheline	1.465
Al2O3(H2O)(s)	Diaspore	1.252	NaAlSiO4(s)	Nepheline	1.465	FeP2(s)	solid	0.5501
FeP2(s)	solid	0.5501	FeP2(s)	solid	0.550	LiAlH4(s)	solid	0.502
LiAlH4(s)	solid	0.502	LiAlH4(s)	solid	0.502	CaS(s)	solid	0.4295
CaS(s)	solid	0.4745	CaS(s)	solid	0.475	MgH2(s)	solid	0.3967
ZnP2(s)	solid	0.423	ZnP2(s)	solid	0.423	As(s)	Rhombohedral	0.387
As(s)	Rhombohedral	0.387	As(s)	Rhombohedral	0.387	P(s)	Solid_(white)	0.3704
TiH2(s)	solid	0.2534	TiH2(s)	solid	0.253	Zn3P2(s)	solid	0.2858
P(s2)	Solid_(red,_V)	0.2332	P(s2)	Solid_(red,_V)	0.233	TiH2(s)	solid	0.2534
KBH4(s)	solid	0.1108	KBH4(s)	solid	0.111	KBH4(s)	solid	0.1108
MnP3(s)	solid	0.1103	MnP3(s)	solid	0.110	MnP3(s)	solid	0.1103
SrH2(s)	solid	5.60E-02	SrH2(s)	solid	0.056	SrS(s)	solid	7.47E-02
ZrH2(s)	solid	3.12E-02	ZrH2(s)	solid	0.031	ZrH2(s)	solid	3.12E-02
BaH2(s)	solid	2.70E-02	BaH2(s)	solid	2.70E-02	BaH2(s2)	solid	2.70E-02
Pb(s)	solid	2.20E-02	Pb(s)	solid	2.20E-02	Pb(s)	solid	2.20E-02
Total mass		92.3684			92.3754			92.3689

Table 10. The results of the sensitivity analysis related to the amount of the oxygen present in the char.

Oxygen content in the feed: 8.90 g			Oxygen content in the feed: 11.9 g			Oxygen content in the feed: 17.9 g		
Chemical formula	Name	Mass	Chemical formula	Name	Mass	Chemical formula	Name	Mass
C(s)	Graphite	54.09	C(s)	Graphite	54.57	C(s)	Graphite	56.21
SiC(s2)	Solid_Beta	8.331	KAlSiO4(s2)	Kaliophilite-or	12.58	KAlSi2O6(s2)	Leucite(RHF)-B	22.48
(CaO)4(Al2O3)(H2O)1	solid	6.347	SiC(s2)	Solid_Beta	6.729	CaCl2(H2O)6(s)	Antarcticite	8.836
KAlSiO4(s2)	Kaliophilite-or	6.256	CaCl2(H2O)6(s)	Antarcticite	6.262	CaMg2Al16O27(s)	solid	2.554
KCl(s)	Sylvite_rocksalt	4.731	(CaO)4(Al2O3)(H2O)1	solid	3.498	(CaO)4(Al2O3)(H2O)1	solid	1.934
AlH3(s)	Solid_(hexagonal)	2.936	CaMg2Al16O27(s)	solid	3.109	Mg5Al2Si3O10(OH)8(s)	clinochlorite	1.727
CaMg2Al16O27(s)	solid	2.776	AlH3(s)	Solid_(hexagona	1.873	NaAlSiO4(s)	Nepheline	1.465
CaCl2(H2O)6(s)	Antarcticite	1.886	KCl(s)	Sylvite_rocksalt	1.752	SiC(s2)	Solid_Beta	1.283
NaAlSiO4(s)	Nepheline	1.465	NaAlSiO4(s)	Nepheline	1.465	AlH3(s)	Solid_(hexagonal)	1.127
FeP2(s)	solid	0.5501	FeP2(s)	solid	0.5501	Al2O3(H2O)(s2)	Boehmite	0.6042
LiAlH4(s)	solid	0.502	LiAlH4(s)	solid	0.502	FeP2(s)	solid	0.5501
CaS(s)	solid	0.4295	CaS(s)	solid	0.4295	LiAlH4(s)	solid	0.502
MgH2(s)	solid	0.3967	As(s)	Rhombohedral	0.387	CaS(s)	solid	0.4295
As(s)	Rhombohedral	0.387	MgH2(s)	solid	0.3783	As(s)	Rhombohedral	0.387
P(s)	Solid_(white)	0.3704	P(s)	Solid_(white)	0.3704	P(s)	Solid_(white)	0.3704
Zn3P2(s)	solid	0.2858	Zn3P2(s)	solid	0.2858	Zn3P2(s)	solid	0.2858
TiH2(s)	solid	0.2534	TiH2(s)	solid	0.2534	TiH2(s)	solid	0.2534
KBH4(s)	solid	0.1108	KBH4(s)	solid	0.1108	KBH4(s)	solid	0.1108
MnP3(s)	solid	0.1103	MnP3(s)	solid	0.1103	MnP3(s)	solid	0.1103
SrS(s)	solid	7.47E-02	SrS(s)	solid	7.47E-02	SrS(s)	solid	7.47E-02
ZrH2(s)	solid	3.12E-02	ZrH2(s)	solid	3.12E-02	ZrH2(s)	solid	3.12E-02
BaH2(s2)	solid	2.70E-02	BaH2(s2)	solid	2.70E-02	BaH2(s2)	solid	2.70E-02
Pb(s)	solid	2.20E-02	Pb(s)	solid	2.20E-02	Pb(s)	solid	2.20E-02
Total mass		92.3689			95.3705			101.3744

8.3 Leaching simulations

In the previous section the simulations of the raw ash composition were described. The selected simulated ash composition was subsequently used as an input for the first water leaching simulations. To match the conditions of the open *in vitro* beaker system (BiV) experiments described in Section 5.2.3, a L/S ratio of 10 was chosen, and two leaching temperatures were applied, namely 25°C and 60°C. The methodology of the simulations was analogous to those described in the section above.

The results of these simulations are presented in **Table 11** to **Table 14**, and consist of an overall mass balance and mass distribution among the solid, aqueous and gas phase (**Table 11**) and the tables with the compositions of the solid phase (**Table 12**), aqueous phase (**Table 13**) and the gas phase (**Table 14**).

The overall mass balance and mass distribution among the phases showed two interesting results. First was the formation of the gas phase, with its mass share in the total system being 0.77% and 0.95% at 25°C and 60°C, respectively. From the gas phase composition results can be seen that a part of this mass share was formed by water vapour, especially at the higher of the temperatures, which is conform the expectations and the observations during the experiment. The highest mass contribution to the gas phase was, however, provided by methane, and the third largest share (in simulations at 60°C) was delivered by CO₂. Especially the presence of methane is unexpected, and was also the reason to perform the experiments in the pressure reactor with gas phase measurements, see Section 6. According to the simulation results the mass of the released methane does not significantly change with the temperature in the simulated temperature range. The release of methane was not confirmed experimentally. The release of CO₂ was partly identified, as described in Section 6.3.1, but the results were not reproducible and also not confirmed by two independent measurement techniques. While the release of CO₂ could be explained by the hypothetical presence of carbonates in the raw substrate and its subsequent release as CO₂ upon the contact with water, the release of methane is more difficult to explain. It was also not found during the review of the relevant literature. Therefore it needs to be investigated which mechanism would be eventually responsible for the presence of methane in the simulated gas composition, and which simulation parameters should be changed to suppress its formation.

Second interesting and important result of the overall mass balance analysis is the increase of the mass of the solids after the simulated leaching. The starting mass was 92.3689 g, and in both simulations the final mass was higher, respectively by 1.2819 g and 1.3317 g at 25°C and 60°C. Since approximately 5 g was transferred into the aqueous phase and ca. 7 to 10 grams into the gas phase, then the net mass increase of the solid must be caused the rearrangement of the elements and an incorporation of the hydrogen and oxygen from the leaching medium (here: water). During the BiV leaching experiments of char in fact in some cases mass increase was observed; unfortunately, no mass of the solid substrate after the MA ash leaching experiments was recorded. This simulation result is important, as it could partly explain the mass balance discrepancies discussed in Section 5.3. There, the final mass of the char after the leaching is an important and sensitive variable. Besides, if during the leaching char or ash composition is changing in other way than just the removal of some elements, then new species constituting the char or ash may form. If this form is more volatile than the previous one, then it may escape the solution upon digestion, leading to biased results of the “left-in-char” composition. This hypothesis will be tested during further implementation of the project.

The analysis of the solid residue composition simulation results also revealed interesting observations. Except C, all compounds underwent a rearrangement, and new compounds were formed during the leaching at 25°C. All potassium remaining in the solid phase formed an aluminosilicate (muscovite), which became the second largest constituent of the solid phase, mainly due to the incorporation of 10 O-atoms and two OH-groups. A similar aluminosilicate is predicted to form a magnesium compound. The metal hydrides were substituted by an oxide (TiO₂, MnTiO₃, Fe₃O₄, AlAsO₄, Ti₂ZrO₆), and sulphides (ZnS, PbS, FeS₂). In the simulation at 60°C, further transformations took place, to carbonates (MnCO₃, FeCO₃)

Finally, the results of the aqueous phase composition shows that all chlorine is mobilised into the solution, accompanied by ca. 32% of the initial amount of potassium. These two elements constitute around 80% of the ions of the aqueous solution. The temperature has a negligible influence on the

composition of the aqueous solution. Further, calcium ions and the boric acid are found in the amounts exceeding 0.1 g. No sulphur, phosphorus, magnesium (apart from a trace amount at 60°C), zinc or lead were predicted to be present in the aqueous phase.

A comparison of the simulation results with the experimental data presented and discussed in Section 5.2 is in a partial agreement with the results, but there are also clear differences:

- potassium recovery in the leachate: simulations showed nearly no dependency on the temperature, yielding a RF of ca. 32%. In the experiments, after a single step a clear temperature dependency was observed, with higher temperature boosting the RF more than two times;
- chlorine: simulations predict full migration into the leachate. Experiments showed that after the first step the RFs are 63%, 67% and 81%, for the 5 minutes, 60 minutes and 24 hours experiments, respectively. In this case the effect of time is clearly visible, and it can be assumed that if the leaching lasted long enough, indeed all the chlorine would migrate into the leachate. Besides, after the second step of the 24 hour experiment (experiment no. 2), the cumulative chlorine concentration in the leachate equalled 94% of the initial amount in the ash. Therefore it can be concluded that the release of chlorine is limited by the kinetics, not the equilibrium;
- sulphur and phosphorus: simulations predicted no S and P in the leachate, while they were consistently measured in the leachates during the experiments. In this case, under the applied modelling parameters no water-soluble sulphur and phosphorus compounds are predicted and the model should be adapted for that purpose;
- magnesium: the release of Mg predicted by the model is minimal at 60°C, while it is found in the leachate during the experiments especially at 25°C. Therefore also here the modelling approach requires additional investigation;
- zinc and lead: these elements are not found in the liquid phase in the simulation results. Also in the experiments no Zn is found in the leachate, while small concentrations of Pb have been measured. Therefore these results suggest that part of the lead is present as a water-soluble compound.

Summarising the results of the first set of the FactSage simulations and their validation against the experimental results it can be concluded that the simulations based on chemical equilibrium and Gibbs' free energy minimization can provide useful insight during the development of the leaching process and the recovery of valuable elements from biomass char and ash. Only the set of results presented above gave multiple suggestions for the required focal points of the research to be implemented during the next stages of the project:

- further characterisation of the solid substrates, in particular to gain additional information about the specific compounds present in the matrix. Probably it would be sufficient to confirm only some of them, as the rest could be calculated / approximated using the model;
- further work on the model to identify which model parameters are determining the presence or absence of specific compounds. Here the analysis of the phase diagrams or similar data available in the literature can provide additional insight and guidelines;
- development of an experimental plan targeted at the validation of the model and the mobility of specific compounds, already mentioned above.
- the investigation of the role of carbon, both in the model and in the actual leaching experiments, and to determine the strategy of either removing the most abundant elements first, or to do "cherry-picking" of the elements of interest from a big and complex matrix, as indicated in **Figure 4**.

Table 11. Overall mass balance and phase distributions resulting from the leaching simulations at 25°C (Simulation1) and 60°C (Simulation 2).

Phase	Simulation 1	Simulation 2
Solid	93.6508	93.7006
Aqueous	914.620	912.640
Gas	7.7892	9.7224
Total output	1016.0600	1016.0630
Char	92.3689	92.3689
Leaching agent (water)	923.689	923.689
Total input	1016.0580	1016.0580

Table 12. Composition of the solid residue (Left in char). Green highlights indicate the presence of new compounds or an increase of their mass in Simulation 2 vs Simulation 1 vs the input. Similarly, red highlights indicate a decrease of the mass.

Simulation 1			Simulation 2		
Chemical formula	Name	Mass	Chemical formula	Name	Mass
C(s)	Graphite	50.7500	C(s)	Graphite	50.6400
Al ₂ O ₃ (H ₂ O)(s)	Diaspore	1.0150	Al ₂ O ₃ (H ₂ O)(s)	Diaspore	1.0040
Mg ₅ Al ₂ Si ₃ O ₁₀ (OH) ₈ (s)	Clinochlorite	2.3220	Mg ₅ Al ₂ Si ₃ O ₁₀ (OH) ₈ (s)	Clinochlorite	2.3200
KAl ₃ Si ₃ O ₁₀ (OH) ₂ (s)	Muscovite	28.4100	KAl ₃ Si ₃ O ₁₀ (OH) ₂ (s)	Muscovite	28.4400
Na ₂ Ca ₃ Si ₆ O ₁₆ (s)	solid	3.0450	Na ₂ Ca ₃ Si ₆ O ₁₆ (s)	solid	2.9880
Ca ₅ HO ₁₃ P ₃ (s)	Hydroxyapatite	4.3120	Ca ₅ HO ₁₃ P ₃ (s)	Hydroxyapatite	4.3120
TiO ₂ (s)	Rutile	0.2945	TiO ₂ (s)	Rutile	0.3523
MnTiO ₃ (s)	Pyrophanite	0.1090	MnCO ₃ (s)	Rhodochrosite	0.07944
Fe ₃ O ₄ (s)	Magnetite	0.2389	FeCO ₃ (s)	Siderite	0.3586
AlAsO ₄ (s)	solid	0.8567	AlAsO ₄ (s)	solid	0.8566
Ti ₂ ZrO ₆ (s)	solid	0.0947	Ti ₂ ZrO ₆ (s)	solid	0.0947
ZnS(s)	Sphalerite	0.3237	ZnS(s)	Sphalerite	0.3237
PbS(s)	solid	0.0254	PbS(s)	solid	0.0254
CaCO ₃ (s)	Aragonite_oP20_	1.6650	CaCO ₃ (s2)	Calcite_hR30_(1	1.7170
FeS ₂ (s)	Pyrite_C2_cP12_	0.1889	FeS ₂ (s)	Pyrite_C2_cP12_	0.1889
Total		93.6508	Total		93.7006

Table 13. Composition of the aqueous phase. Mass cut-off at 0.001 g of the compound in the solution. Concentrations in g/kg solution. Mass in grams.

Simulation 1			Simulation 2		
Chemical formula	Concentration	Mass	Chemical formula	Concentration	Mass
Cl[-]	3.1451	2.877	Cl[-]	3.152	2.877
K[+]	1.4501	1.326	K[+]	1.4506	1.324
Ca[2+]	0.71365	0.653	Ca[2+]	0.70541	0.644
H ₃ BO ₃	0.11668	0.107	H ₃ BO ₃	0.13703	0.125
Li[+]	0.10094	0.092	Li[+]	0.10116	0.092
Sr[2+]	6.01E-02	0.055	Sr[2+]	6.03E-02	0.055
Ba[2+]	2.93E-02	0.027	H ₄ SiO ₄	3.13E-02	0.029
CH ₄	2.14E-02	0.020	Ba[2+]	2.93E-02	0.027
BO ₂ [-]	1.45E-02	0.013	H ₂ SiO ₃	2.39E-02	0.022
H ₄ SiO ₄	9.40E-03	0.009	CH ₄	1.15E-02	0.010
H ₂ SiO ₃	6.82E-03	0.006	HCO ₃ [-]	8.12E-03	0.007
HCO ₃ [-]	2.16E-03	0.002	Na[+]	5.01E-03	0.005
H ₂ BO ₃ [-]	2.03E-03	0.002	Mn[2+]	3.30E-03	0.003
Mn[2+]	1.39E-03	0.001	BO ₂ [-]	1.78E-03	0.002
			Mg[2+]	8.31E-04	0.001
Total (ions)		5.189	Total (ions)		5.222
Total (solution)		914.62	Total (solution)		912.64

Table 14. Composition of the gaseous phase.

Simulation 1			Simulation 2		
Chemical formula	Mole fraction	Mass	Chemical formula	Mole fraction	Mass
CH ₄ (g)	96.83%	7.51E+00	CH ₄ (g)	80.07%	7.59E+00
H ₂ O(g)	3.1675%	2.76E-01	H ₂ O(g)	19.84%	2.11E+00
H ₂ (g)	35.152ppm	3.43E-05	CO ₂ (g)	738.69ppm	1.92E-02
CO ₂ (g)	8.2163ppm	1.75E-04	H ₂ (g)	157.93ppm	1.88E-04
H ₂ S(g)	19.604ppb	3.23E-07	H ₂ S(g)	599.48ppb	1.21E-05
C ₂ H ₆ (g)	24.517ppb	3.57E-07	C ₂ H ₆ (g)	59.250ppb	1.05E-06
Total (gas)			Total (gas)		9.7224

9 Conclusions

This report presented the results of the first part of the research work performed to explore the recovery of valuable elements from solid gasification residues (char, ashes) via leaching. This research was implemented as a part of the work in WP7 of the BeBOP project (WP7, *Enabling technologies at lab-scale for SOEC characterisation and resource recovery, T7.2, Recovery elements from solid gasification residues via leaching*), and included experimental laboratory work as well as modelling and simulations. The following can be concluded from the implemented research work:

The elemental analysis of the char and ash is crucial for the assessment of the leaching potential, and the efficiency of the leaching process. The results, partly already presented in the deliverable D7.3 revealed differences in the quantification of the inorganic elements. These differences in some cases were reaching even up to an order of magnitude, which significantly complicated a reliable analysis of the leaching efficiency. Nonetheless, one reference set of results (delivered by the ETL lab) was selected for this analysis which allowed the comparison of different leaching conditions and the observation of the trends. This, in turn allowed the conclusions which process conditions were affecting the leaching behaviour of the selected elements the most.

The recovered fraction (RF) was the main result to compare the effectiveness and efficiency of the leaching parameters. The water leaching experiments in the batch *in vitro* system showed that for the mobilisation of the selected elements from the solid into the leachate the leaching time is of secondary importance. What contributed more to the cumulative RF, were sequences of leaching and inter-step drying. In this way, a similar RF of potassium, sulphur, phosphorus and magnesium could be reached in five subsequent 5-minute steps, as in five 60-minute steps. Even two 24-hour steps, tested for the leaching of MA did not give higher RF values. In the case of phosphorus, the first inter-step drying was even identified as an enabler for the release of the element into the leachate in the following leaching step.

Multiple process parameters influenced the RF. First, the type of substrate. For example, full potassium recovery was measured in case of MA after 5 water leaching steps, 80-90% from HAY and MMX chars, while only just above 40% from the DW char. DW and CW yielded the highest RFs for the sulphur, around 80% at maximum. Highest phosphorus RF was achieved for MMX char, nearly 20%. The effect of elevated leaching temperature with water on the maximum cumulative RF showed a clear positive effect in the case of potassium and sulphur, neutral effect in the case of phosphorus and magnesium and a negative effect in the case of lead, which is very positive from the separation of the individual elements point of view, and especially the separation of the nutrients from (toxic) heavy metals.

Of the **reagents applied in the second leaching step**, the acids CA, OA and HCl have a positive, but combined effect on the recovery of phosphorus and metals (Zn, Mn, Mg and Al). Lead was only mobilised into the leachate using CA and HCl, not with OA. With NaOH an RF of 30% was reached for aluminium, but only in CW; apart from that, NaOH did not yield any prospective results. With EDTA ca. 35% RF of phosphorus was achieved but only for MMX; further it also contributed to the RFs of Zn and Ca, but did not perform as well as other leaching agents. AA gave the best results in potassium and sulphur leaching, however these elements can be also leached using water as shown above.

The analysis of the mass balance closure, i.e. the elemental balances revealed large differences between the mass balances calculated using the leachate analysis and using the “left-in-char” analyses. The main reason for this was the analysis of the raw char and also of the intermediate char samples (between the subsequent leaching steps). The uncertainties about the digestion procedure add to the total uncertainty and the magnitude of the measurement error. During the analysis no element was identified that could act as a reliable “internal standard” to be used for the closure of the mass balance and for the use of data reconciliation techniques. Nonetheless a further investigation of this aspect is planned in the future work.

The first set of the FactSage™ simulations provided modelling results for the water leaching of MA. The simulations confirmed the mass increase of the solid substrate after the leaching, also observed during some leaching experiments. Furthermore, substantial gas release was observed, mainly of the methane. This was not confirmed experimentally, but the release of CO₂ during the leaching at 60°C was observed during one of the experiments. The results for the aqueous phase revealed only the presence of the chlorine, potassium, and calcium ions, while the experiments clearly indicated the presence of other elements. This can be attributed to the model composition of the solid substrate, which was also calculated using FactSage™ based on the elemental analyses – clearly this model needs further fine-tuning before the leaching process can be reliably modelled. Therefore, further characterisation of the solid substrates, in particular to gain additional information about the specific compounds present in the matrix will be necessary. Probably it would be sufficient to confirm only some of them, as the rest could be calculated / approximated using the model.

In general, it can be concluded that each leaching sequence will start with water leaching, likely followed by the second water of AA step to remove all potassium, chlorine and sulphur. Then, preferably other nutrient elements (phosphorus, magnesium, calcium) should be recovered, finally followed by other (heavy) metals. At this stage it is not yet possible to draw conclusions about the procedures for other important elements present in the char and ash, namely silicon and aluminium. Their mobilisation into the leachate as its justification is yet to be investigated. The exact process equipment (open system or pressurized reactor) is still to be defined. The open system performed relatively well considering its simplicity, but high temperature (200°C) and pressurized conditions had a significant positive effect on the recovery fraction of potassium and sulphur. Likely solely the higher RFs of these two elements will not justify the engagement of such more complex equipment, but the final choice will depend on the overall recovery scheme and any possible process integrations (e.g., thermal integration) with the gasification or the entire bio/e-methanol production facility.

Finally, it is decided for the future leaching experiments to perform only the ICP analyses of the leachate. The cuvette tests are sufficiently reliable for the analyses of the aqueous leachates, but return only limited range of elements, while often showing undesirable interaction with other leaching agents.

The results obtained in this part of the project will be used for the further investigation of the recovery of the elements via leaching, namely in WP8 of the project (WP8, *Technology validation: SOEC and gasification residues recovery*, T8.2, *Leaching conditions validation*).

10 Literature list

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11 Appendix I: ICP results

Concentrations of inorganic (trace) elements in biomass and char samples determined by ICP-OES – PPNT laboratory (mg/g dry basis). Note: blank column means that the sample was not analysed.

Element	MMX	CW	HAY	DW	MMX Char	CW Char	HAY Char	DW Char
Si	22.5	0.150			43.9	0.751		
Al	0.286	0.178			0.703	0.483		
K	5.59	0.211			22.5	2.34		
Ca	4.39	1.74			14.4	8.47		
P	1.30	<LOD			3.91	1.04		
Mg	0.581	0.222			2.06	1.04		
Fe	0.333	0.159			0.832	0.0711		
Ti	0.0138	<LOD			0.129	<LOD		
Na	0.220	0.435			1.66	1.45		
Zn	0.374	0.0127			0.753	0		
S	1.72	0.275			3.91	0.312		
Li	n.m.	n.m.			n.m.	n.m.		
Sr	0.0107	<LOD			<LOD	<LOD		
Mn	0.0248	0.0761			0.103	0.367		
Ba	n.m.	n.m.			<LOD	0.310		
B	<LOD	0.0745			0.347	0.212		
Pb	0.0194	<LOD			0.147	0.0906		
As	n.m.	n.m.			n.m.	n.m.		
Cd	n.m.	n.m.			n.m.	n.m.		
Cr	<LOD	0.0234			0.535	0.139		
Ni	0.184	0.0244			n.m.	n.m.		
Zr	n.m.	n.m.			n.m.	n.m.		
Co	<LOD	0.0239			<LOD	0.0711		
Se	n.m.	n.m.			<LOD	0.0627		
Bi	<LOD	0.0178			n.m.	n.m.		
Cu	n.m.	n.m.			n.m.	n.m.		
Mo	0.0119	<LOD			<LOD	<LOD		
Hg	n.m.	n.m.			n.m.	n.m.		
Sb	n.m.	n.m.			n.m.	n.m.		
Sn	n.m.	n.m.			n.m.	n.m.		
V	n.m.	n.m.			n.m.	n.m.		

Concentrations of inorganic (trace) elements in biomass and char samples determined by ICP-OES – IL laboratory (mg/g dry basis). Note: blank column means that the sample was not analysed.

Element	MMX	CW	HAY	DW	MMX Char	CW Char	HAY Char	DW Char
Si			19.3	5.43	31.6	9.56	32.1	10.8
Al			0.608	0.0255	0.115	0.0437	3.46	0.0884
K			2.65	0.107	1.81	0.145	4.78	0.156
Ca			1.73	0.567	1.17	0.502	2.44	0.671
P			0.102	0.00139	0.0459	0.00347	0.222	0.00141
Mg			0.576	0.125	0.295	0.0941	0.916	0.0781
Fe			0.860	0.450	0.304	0.0534	2.06	0.749
Ti			<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Na			4.90	0.634	2.20	0.514	8.91	0.828
Zn			0.0175	0.0254	0.264	0.00541	0.0376	0.0673
S			0.958	0.136	0.193	0.0322	1.06	0.218
Li			<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Sr			0.0160	0.00241	0.0141	0.00148	0.0483	0.00303
Mn			0.169	0.101	0.0449	0.0459	0.366	0.0553
Ba			0.0125	0.00365	0.0379	0.0163	0.0398	0.00893
B			0.0105	0.00442	0.00566	0.00267	0.0328	0.00341
Pb			0.00160	0.00198	0.0155	0.00143	0.0048	0.00275
As			0.00090	0.00058	0.00132	0.00098	<LOD	0.00105
Cd			0.00045	0.00032	0.00043	<LOD	0.00107	0.00022
Cr			0.00657	0.00079	0.0221	0.00056	0.0180	0.00123
Ni			0.00020	<LOD	<LOD	0.00419	0.00158	<LOD
Zr			<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Co			0.00011	0.00701	<LOD	0.00013	0.00046	0.00464
Se			0.00219	0.00064	<LOD	<LOD	0.00035	<LOD
Bi			<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Cu			0.00605	0.00225	0.00282	0.00075	0.0132	0.0108
Mo			0.00071	<LOD	0.00026	<LOD	0.00155	<LOD
Hg			0.00019	0.00020	0.00021	0.00020	0.00020	0.00021
Sb			<LOD	0.00025	0.00062	0.00047	<LOD	0.00023
Sn			0.00412	0.00387	0.00488	0.00505	0.00523	0.00481
V			0.00251	0.00222	0.00175	0.00205	0.00699	0.00209

Concentrations of inorganic (trace) elements in biomass and char samples determined by ICP-OES – ETL laboratory (mg/g dry basis). Note: blank column means that the sample was not analysed.

Element	MMX	CW	HAY	DW	MMX Char	CW Char	HAY Char	DW Char
Si					14.7	0.499	16.6	1.086
Al					0.161	0.096	5.01	0.214
K					14.8	1.555	43.8	0.782
Ca					6.864	2.583	24.4	4.22
P					1.75	0.202	8.127	0.136
Mg					1.16	0.591	6.094	0.645
Fe					0.378	0.065	3.9	2.457
Ti					n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.
Na					0.074	0.111	1.805	0.184
Zn					0.448	<LOD	0.08	0.12
S					0.73	0.091	1.346	0.404
Li					<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Sr					<LOD	<LOD	0.038	<LOD
Mn					0.054	0.218	0.369	0.255
Ba					0.057	0.031	0.055	0.028
B					<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Pb					0.039	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
As					<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Cd					<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Cr					<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Ni					<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Zr					n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.
Co					<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	0.039
Se					n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.
Bi					n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.
Cu					<LOD	<LOD	0.021	0.04
Mo					n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.
Hg					n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.
Sb					n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.
Sn					n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.
V					<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD

Concentrations of inorganic (trace) elements in biomass and char samples determined by ICP-OES – IETU laboratory (mg/g dry basis). Note: blank column means that the sample was not analysed.

Element	MMX	CW	HAY	DW	MMX Char	CW Char	HAY Char	DW Char
Si								
Al					0.23	0.0618	4.97	0.206
K					13.2	1.21	47.4	0.650
Ca					4.82	1.99	23.8	2.78
P					2.15	0.261	7.55	0.156
Mg					1.49	0.749	5.09	0.689
Fe					0.394	0.0842	3.67	2.07
Ti					0.0186	0.0016	0.352	0.054
Na					0.148	0.111	3.11	0.292
Zn					0.369	0.0057	0.078	0.0986
S								
Li						0.0002	0.0113	0.0027
Sr					0.0239	0.0085	0.0491	0.0133
Mn					0.0629	0.263	0.415	0.282
Ba					0.0555	0.027	0.137	0.0241
B					0.0054	0.0044	0.0304	0.0064
Pb					0.0184		0.0023	0.0015
As							0.001	
Cd								
Cr					0.0026	0.0005	0.0154	0.0021
Ni					0.0005		0.0047	0.0007
Zr								
Co							0.0007	0.0119
Se								
Bi								
Cu					0.0027	0.0004	0.011	0.0196
Mo					0.0017	0.0001	0.004	0.0005
Hg								
Sb								
Sn								0.0005
V							0.0062	

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